

PAN African University
Life and Earth Sciences Institute
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**ASSESSING URBAN RENEWAL AS A TOOL FOR
ENVIRONMENTAL MANAGEMENT;
A CASE STUDY OF NAIROBI COUNTY, KENYA.**

By

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DECLARATION

I declare that this dissertation is my original work and I affirm that it has not been presented in any other University for examination or for any other purpose. This work forms part of the fulfilment of the requirements for the award of the Degree of Master of Science in ENVIRONMENTAL MANAGEMENT, Pan African University Life and Earth Sciences Institute (PAULESI), University of Ibadan.

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DEDICATION

I cannot help but dedicate this work to:

My lovely Parents, Diephens and Becky, my Parents in Law, Thomas and Agnes, all my

Brothers and Sisters,

My unborn baby who has always accompanied me through all the rigor of thesis writing with
supportive kicks and knocks, and

My best friend and husband Wilson Ombati, who besides persistently pressing me to work
harder, his consistent love, prayers, encouragement and assurance went a long way in helping me
accomplish this study in a country thousands of miles away from home.

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

DECLARATION	i
DEDICATION	ii
ACKNOWLEDGEMENT	iii
TABLE OF CONTENTS.....	iv
LIST OF TABLES	viii
LIST OF FIGURES	x
LIST OF PLATES	xii
ACRONYMS	xiii
ABSTRACT.....	xiv
CHAPTER ONE	1
1. INTRODUCTION	1
1.1 Background to the Study.....	1
1.2 Statement of the Research Problem	2
1.3 Justification and Significance for the Study	4
1.4 Aim and Objectives.....	6
1.5 Research Hypotheses	6
1.6 Research Methodology	6
1.6.1 Research Design.....	6
1.6.2 Target Population.....	7
1.6.3 Sample Size.....	7
1.6.4 Sampling Procedure	8
1.6.5 Research Instruments	9

1.6.6 Pilot Study.....	10
1.7 Context of the Study	12
1.7.1 Profile of Nairobi and an Overview of the Study Area	12
1.7.2 Case Study Areas:	16
CHAPTER TWO	23
2. THEORETICAL REVIEW AND CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK	23
2.1 Theoretical Framework.....	23
2.2 Conceptual Framework.....	26
2.3 Concept of Environmental Management	27
2.3.1 Definition of environmental management	27
2.3.2 Environmental Management Infrastructure in Kenya.....	27
2.4 Concept of Urban Renewal.....	28
2.4.1 Urban Renewal Strategies.....	29
2.5 Literature Review.....	32
2.5.1 Urban Renewal and Environmental Management in America	32
2.5.2 Urban Renewal and Environmental Management in Europe	34
2.5.3 Urban Renewal and Environmental Management in Asia.....	35
2.5.4 Urban Renewal and Environmental Management in Africa.....	37
CHAPTER THREE	46
3. Socio-Economic, Housing And Basic Urban Environmental Characteristics	46
3.1 General Information.....	46
3.2 Socio-Economic Characteristics	46
3.3 Housing Characteristics	52
3.4 Basic Urban Environmental Characteristics	61
3.4.1 Water.....	61
3.4.2 Market.....	73

3.4.3 Waste Management.....	82
3.4.4 Drainage.....	89
CHAPTER FOUR.....	97
4. HEALTH, ENERGY, SECURITY, ENVIRONMENTAL AWARENESS, AND FIRE ATTRIBUTES OF THE AREA.	97
4.1 Health Issues.....	97
4.1.1 Cases and Type of Disease Outbreak.....	97
4.2 Energy.....	101
4.2.1 Source of energy for cooking and heating.....	101
4.3 Security.....	109
4.3.1 Accessibility of Locality.....	111
4.4 Fire Services.....	114
4.5 Preservation.....	117
4.6 Environmental Awareness.....	121
CHAPTER FIVE.....	124
5. SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS.....	124
5.1 Summary.....	124
5.1.1 Socio-economic, Housing and Basic Urban Environmental Characteristics.....	124
5.1.2 Health, Energy, Security, Environmental Awareness Of The Residents, And Fire Attributes Of The Area.	127
5.2 Conclusions.....	128
5.3 Recommendations.....	129
5.3.1. Policy Reform.	129
5.3.2 Urban Planning.	130
5.3.3 Host Country Ownership.	130
5.3.4 Research Gaps.....	130

REFERENCES	131
APPENDICES	142
APPENDIX 1: QUESTIONNAIRE	142
APPENDIX 2: FOCUS GROUP DISCUSSIONS	148
APPENDIX 3: KEY INFORMANT SCHEDULE.....	151
APPENDIX 4: OTHER FIGURES.....	152
APPENDIX 5: PLANS	156
APPENDIX 6: DAILY NATION NEWS EXCERPT	122

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1.1 Research Instruments to Address the Research Objectives	9
Table 1.2 Population trends (census) in Kenya and Nairobi	14
Table 1.3 Population Projections in Nairobi.....	14
Table 3.1 Number and Percentage of respondents in the Sampled sites	46
Table 3.2 Respondents' Level of Education in the different sites	49
Table 3.3 Respondents Occupation Instances for in the Different Sites.....	51
Table 3.4 Type of Previous House for Respondents in Specific Segments.....	55
Table 3.5 Respondents View on the Structural Condition of the Building They Used To Live In Before.....	60
Table 3.6 Previous Source of Drinking Water for the Respondents.....	63
Table 3.7 Current Source of Drinking Water for the Respondents.....	64
Table 3.8 showing Chi-square Tests result on previous and current water sources	64
Table 3.9 Frequency of Piped Water Flow in the Previous Residence.....	65
Table 3.10 Frequency of Piped Water Flow In The Current Area.....	65
Table 3.11 Paired T Test on Frequency of Flow of Piped Water	66
Table 3.12 Monthly Water Payment in the Previous Residence	67
Table 3.13 Monthly Water Payment in the Current Residence	67
Table 3.14 Paired T Test on Water Payment	68
Table 3.15 Paired T-Test on Distance to Water Source.....	70
Table 3.16 Paired T- Tests on Distance to Nearest Retail Shop for Daily Supplies.....	78
Table 3.17 Previous Market Condition.....	80
Table 3.18 General Views on the Market Environment	80
Table 3.19 Chi-Square Test on Market Condition.....	81
Table 3.20 Chi-Square Tests on Methods of Waste Collection.....	83
Table 3.21 Frequency of Waste Collection in the Previous Slum Area	85
Table 3.22 Paired T-Tests On Frequency Of Waste Collection	85
Table 3.23 Frequency of Waste Collection in the Current Area.....	86
Table 3.24 Type of Toilet Facility in the Previous Residence.....	89
Table 3.25 Chi-Square Test on the Type of Toilet Facility	91
Table 3.26 Chi-Square Test on the Type of Drainage System	94

Table 4.1 Specific Disease Outbreak	98
Table 4.2 Chi-Square Test on Disease Outbreak	97
Table 4.3 Chi-Square Tests On Nearby Health Facilities.....	98
Table 4.4 Chi-Square Test on the Views Concerning the State Of The Health Facilities	99
Table 4.5:Previous Source(s) of Energy	105
Table 4.6 Other Previous Source of Energy	105
Table 4.7 Current Overall Source of Energy	107
Table 4.8 Other Source of Energy Being Used Currently	107
Table 4.9 Chi-Square Test on Source of Energy for Cooking and Heating	108
Table 4.10 Chi-Square Test on Accessibility of Locality.....	114
Table 4.11 Overall Previous Cases of Fire Outbreaks.....	115
Table 4.12 Chi-Square Test on Cases of Fire Outbreak	115
Table 4.13 Views on Recreational Facilities in the Previous Areas	119
Table 4.14 Views on Recreational Facilities in the Current Areas.....	119
Table 4.15 Chi-Square Tests on Preservation.....	119
Table 4.16 Previous Media of Information on Environmental Issues	121
Table 4.17 Current Media for Environmental Sensitization.....	122
Table 4.18 Chi-Square Test on Availability of Information for Environmental Sensitization...	123

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1.1 Location of the City of Nairobi	13
Figure 1.2 Image Digitization of the Encroached 60m-Wide Railway Reserve.	18
Figure 1.3 Residential Floor Plan	19
Figure 1.4 Business Stall Floor Plan,.....	20
Figure 1.5 Makongeni and Mbotela Segment.....	21
Figure 1.6 Kianda and Soweto Area.....	22
Figure 2.1 Conceptual Framework	26
Figure 3.1 Gender Percentage (%).....	47
Figure 3.2 Age Of Respondents.....	47
Figure 3.3 Marital Status of the Respondents.....	48
Figure 3.4 Respondents' Level of Education.....	49
Figure 3.5 Religion Indices.....	50
Figure 3.6 Occupation of Residents.....	50
Figure 3.7 Average Monthly Income.....	51
Figure 3.8 Number of Occupants in the Previous House.....	56
Figure 3.9 Nature of occupancy.....	57
Figure 3.10 Monthly Rent Paid By Respondents in Their Previous Residence	58
Figure 3.11 Age of Building in Years.....	59
Figure 3.12 Material Used for Wall Construction of the Respondent's Houses	59
Figure 3.13 Views Concerning the Previous State	61
Figure 3.14 Comparison between Previous and Current Distance to Water Source	69
Figure 3.15 Previous Distance to Water Source.	70
Figure 3.16 Current Distance to Water Source in the Different Segments.....	71
Figure 3.17 Views on Current Water Supply.....	72
Figure 3.18 Views on Current Water Supply in the Different Segments	73
Figure 3.19: Previous and Current Distance to the Market	76
Figure 3.20 Previous vs Current Distances to Retail Market.....	77
Figure 3.21 Current Market Environment	81
Figure 3.22 Previous Method of Waste Collection.....	82
Figure 3.23 Frequency of Waste Collection in the Previous Residence.....	83

Figure 3.24 Current Method of Waste Collection	84
Figure 3.25 Current Frequency of Waste Collection	84
Figure 3.26 Views on Waste Collection in the New Area.....	86
Figure 3.27 Views on Waste Collection in the Current Residence.....	88
Figure 3.28 Previous Mode of Toilet Usage.....	89
Figure 3.29 Previous Type of Drainage System	93
Figure 3.30 Views on the Condition of the Drainage System in the Previous Residence.....	93
Figure 3.31 Current Type of Drainage System.....	94
Figure 3.32 Views on Current Condition of the Drainage System	95
Figure 4.1 Per cent Respondents That Had Witnessed Disease Outbreaks in the Previous Residence.	97
Figure 4.2 Respondents Who Have Witnessed Disease Outbreaks in the Current Area	97
Figure 4.3 Nearby Health Facility	99
Figure 4.4 Views on the State of the Previous Health Facility.....	100
Figure 4.5 Views on the State of the Current Health Facility.....	101
Figure 4.6 Source of Energy for the Respondents In Both Previous And Current Residence ...	105
Figure 4.7 Level of Security in the Previous Area.....	109
Figure 4.8 Level of Security in the Current Residence.....	110
Figure 4.9 Current Level of Security	110
Figure 4.10 Respondents Who Had Problem of Accessing Their Previous Locality	112
Figure 4.11 Reasons Of Inaccessibility in Both Previous And Current Locality	112
Figure 4.12 Recreational Facilities in the Previous Area	117
Figure 4.13 Recreational Facilities in the Current Residence.....	118
Figure 4.14 Respondents Sensitized on Environmental Issues.....	121
Figure 4.15 Percent (%) of Respondents informed on Environmental Sensitization in the Previous Residence	122

LIST OF PLATES

Plate 3.1 Frail Structures in Mukuru Kwa Njenga slum.....	52
Plate 3.2 Poor Spacing of Structures in Soweto East.....	53
Plate 3.3 Tin and paper roofs in Mukuru Kwa Njenga Slum.....	54
Plate 3.4 People Queueing to Buy Water.....	62
Plate 3.5 Water Meter Kiosk In Kibera.	62
Plate 3.6 Soweto East Residents’ Structures Proximity to the Retail Shops.	74
Plate 3.7 Mukuru Kwa Njenga ‘Soko Ya Reli’ Market Area	75
Plate 3.8 Mukuru Kwa Reuben ‘Soko Ya Reli’ Market Area	75
Plate 3.9 Heavy Traffic Using the Railway for Transit.	79
Plate 3.10 Mukuru Kwa Sinai Railway Line Encroached By Business Activity.	79
Plate 3.11 RAP Buildings Facing Away From the Railway Line.	87
Plate 3.12 Fresh Life Public Toilet in Mukuru Slum.....	90
Plate 3.13 Lack of Sewer in the Slum.....	92
Plate 3.14 Sewer and Drainage connections in the RAP Units.....	96
Plate 4.1 Open Dumping And Risky Drains.....	98
Plate 4.2 Sewer In Front Of House	99
Plate 4.3 Illegal Electricity Connections in Mukuru Sinai	106
Plate 4.4 Illegal Electricity Connections In Soweto East,	107
Plate 4.5 Poor Road Accessibility Due To Poor Drainage	113
Plate 4.6 Inadequate Dev. Control Mechanisms, Waste Dumping.....	113
Plate 4.7 A Power Meter for a Single Unit	116
Plate 4.8 Power Board.....	116
Plate 4.9 Children Playing Outside the RAP Units	120

ACRONYMS

AC	Awareness of Consequences
AR	Ascription of Responsibility
EATTFP	East Africa Trade and Transport Facilitation Project
EMS	Environmental Management System
EMCA	Environmental Management and Coordination Act
FGDs	Focus Group Discussions
MDGs	Millennium Development Goals
KNBS	Kenya National Bureau of Statistics
KRC	Kenya Railways Corporation
LPG	Liquefied Petroleum Gas
NHC	National Housing Corporation
NEMA	National Environmental Management Authority
NGO	Non- Governmental Organisation
NEP	New Environmental (or Ecological) Paradigm
UN	United Nations
NCC	Nairobi City County
PAPs	Project Affected Persons
PN	Personal Norms
REMU	Relocation Management Unit
RVR	Rift Valley Railways
SDI	Slum Dwellers International
VBN	Value- Based- Norm Theory

ABSTRACT

Urban renewal (UR) refers to the diversified efforts to eliminate and prevent slums and blight, whether residential or non-residential, and the removal of the factors that create such slums and blighting conditions. In various settings of the world, it is executed through several strategies or approaches including redevelopment, rehabilitation and conservation (of monuments), spot clearance and revitalization. Urban renewal has been considered to be a sound approach that promotes land values and enhance the environmental quality. Indeed, this concept of has lately become of key concern amongst professionals in the built and non- built environment on the demand about its sustainability due to the rapid urbanization instances of cities in the world.

The objective of this research is to assess the effectiveness of Urban renewal as a tool for environmental management. Using Nairobi County, Kenya as a case study, the selected sample sites were Makongeni, Mbotela, Kianda and Soweto East segments of The Relocation Action Plan project by The Kenya Railways Corporation (KRC). The residents in these segments had relocated from the railway reserve in either Kibera slum or Mukuru Slum both in Nairobi County.

To undertake this research, a cross sectional survey research design that encompassed the use of both primary and secondary data collection methods was employed. A household survey entailing the issuing out of 384 questionnaires to sampled out residents from the four segments was conducted. The research adopted the Value Based Norm (VBN) Theory by Stern, which postulates that bearing and perceiving adverse effects from a certain environmental challenge can promote mitigation behavior.

Descriptive Statistics and inferential statistics were used to analyze whether the implementation of Urban renewal strategies has created significant difference between the environment in previous and the current areas of residence. Indeed, the findings of this research confirm part of the research's original expectations. That is, Urban renewal, smartly effected can be a tool for environmental management. The recommendations of this research outlined in Chapter five of this dissertation can be used as an important manuscript to strengthen the understanding of experts in the built and non-built environment on planning for environmentally sustainable UR projects.

CHAPTER ONE

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the Study

Global trends show that more people live in the urban areas than in rural areas, and this might continue into the future. For example, in 1950, 30 per cent of the world's population was urban. In 2014, 54 per cent of the world's population resided in urban areas, and it is further projected to rise to 66 per cent by 2050 (UN, 2014). The world population is projected to increase by more than one billion people within the next 15 years, reaching 8.5 billion in 2030, to increase further to 9.7 billion in 2050 and 11.2 billion by 2100. More than half of global population growth between now and 2050 is however expected to occur in Africa which has the highest rate of population growth among major areas, growing at a pace of 2.55 per cent annually in 2010-2015 (UN, 2015). This increasing world population is expected to exponentially increase the urban population especially in Africa and in Asia.

The UN projections suggest that Africa will enter its urban age by 2035 when 50 per cent of the population will live in urban areas. African cities with less than 500,000 inhabitants are now absorbing about two-thirds of all urban population growth. However, Africa's larger cities continue to grow fast as well. In 2005, Africa had 43 cities with more than one million inhabitants, up from 28 a decade earlier. Today 2016, Africa is home to mega urban projects such as Ghana's Hope City and Appolonia King City, Nigeria's Eko-Atlantic City, Kenya's Konza and Tatu Cities, Congo's La Cite du Fleuve. Traditional city-based urbanization is moving towards regional urbanization patterns, including the emergence of city regions, urban corridors, and mega urban regions as mentioned above (UN ECOSOC, 2014).

All of these have resulted to the growth of informal and unregulated urban settlements, contributing to the degradation of the environment in African cities. The most immediate and pressing challenge is to improve the environmental conditions of the urban poor. The urban poor live in life-threatening conditions with limited access to clean water, adequate drainage and sanitation. They are also affected by high levels of pollution due to toxic materials, traffic and industrial emissions, residential congestions, and absence of green spaces (Hardoy, Mitlin, and Satterthwaite, 2003). The result is environmental degradation, increased natural and manmade

disaster, scarcity of drinking water and increased risk of public health (UN ECOSOC, 2014). Rapid urbanization also implies excessive strain on existing infrastructure, increased demand for energy, land and natural resources; traffic congestion, due to a growing dependence on motor vehicles and intensive use of fossil fuels (Freire, Lall, and Leipziger, 2014)

As the world moves into the urban age, the dynamism and intense vitality of cities become even more prominent. A fresh future is taking shape, with urban areas around the world becoming not just the dominant form of habitat for humankind, but also the engine-rooms of human development as a whole (UN Habitat, 2013).

Efforts at reshaping African cities, new communities, housing projects which fosters in depth consideration and the kind of environment being envisaged for the future generations is imperative (Masayo and Holly, 2014). Accordingly, urban development is increasingly attracting attention as nations and cities fight the challenges of sustainability, including the burden of environmental management.

1.2 Statement of the Research Problem

Early in the year 2009, the United Nations Environmental Programme in Nairobi reported that rapid population growth in Nairobi has outstripped the city's ability to deliver adequate basic services such as education, shelter, health care, safe water, sanitation, and waste management resulting to urban decay. Of key concern is the fact that as the city continues to grow, it faces the challenge of planning for sustainable urban development that provides for adequate housing and services and at the same time protect the natural environment within and around the city (NCC, 2014). According to this research, this has resulted to the most visible characteristic of urban decay in Nairobi, the creation and sprawl of informal settlements in Kenya's capital city over the years.

According to CCN (2007), by 1995 there were a total of 134 informal settlements in Nairobi with 77,589 structures having a combined population of 1,886,166. These informal settlements/slums mostly occupied the poorest quality lands such as riparian reserves, swamps, steep slopes, refilled quarries and garbage dumps since there were no existing formal systems put in place to provide affordable serviced land for the new immigrants. Similarly, settlements spilled over to

service reserves like railway safety zones, pipeline passage points, land under high voltage power lines and on road reserves (Irene and Jack, 2010).

Currently, the informal settlements in the city have perpetually sprawled outwards, further endangering the environment by taking over the forested and agricultural lands, while fragmenting and degrading the remaining natural areas resulting to urban decay. Today, they host close to 29% of the total city's population (NCC, 2014). In these informal settlements, residents are exposed to overcrowded conditions with remarkably poor unsanitary living conditions, improper garbage disposal, inadequate and unsafe water, polluted air, make-shift shelters, unstable social networks, and environmental diseases like cholera, dysentery, and typhoid (NCC, 2014).

In several cases, the Government of Kenya has interposed in creating development plans and programs to avert the challenges of urban decay. One of the mechanisms is the implementation of urban renewal interventions (NEMA, 2003). In Nairobi city specifically, urban renewal interventions have been implemented by the county government, companies and individuals in several areas. However, as recognized, most of these interventions seem to adopt an individualistic or piecemeal approach where plot owners seek to develop their own plot under their own initiatives; basically due to the realization by developers of the high value of lands. This is the key motivator of these renewal projects. Karanja (2014) notes that most of these renewal projects adopt the redevelopment approach where the existing old and low rise buildings are demolished to pave way for the high rise developments.

In Nairobi, urban renewal, like many other development initiatives, is aimed at improving the quality of lives of the targeted individuals and it mostly focuses on addressing the challenge of urban decay (Olima, 2001). So much has been done in Nairobi to curb the problem of the proliferation of the informal settlements which, as stated earlier, serves to be the most visible characteristic of urban decay in Nairobi. Despite of these and since the implementation of these programs, there has not been a clear documentation of strategies that have been implemented in Nairobi at large by the Government or companies pertaining to this challenge and whether or not these programs are effective in solving the environmental challenges that characterise urban decay.

Accordingly, research examines pockets of urban renewal activities that have been implemented in Kenya's capital, Nairobi, with a special focus on how it has contributed towards solving the contemporary environmental challenges. Cases of the Relocation Action Plan (RAP) units of the Kenya Railways Corporation (KRC) in conjunction with the Ministry of Transport found at Makongeni, Mbotela and Kibera areas of Nairobi were selected as the sample study areas of Nairobi. This research argues that in this time and era, it is important that environmental sustainability strategies are mandatorily integrated in urban renewal activities.

1.3 Justification and Significance for the Study

Urban renewal is a crucial aspect of urban development and planning. Anna Tibaijuka, Executive Director UN Habitat and Director General UN reported this, adding that cities can achieve a more sustainable land use if municipalities can actually combine urban planning and development with environmental management (Dodman, Barry, McGranahan, and IIED, 2013).

As stated before, majority of Nairobi's divisions (Pumwani, Makongeni, Kibera, Dagoretti and Kasarani) are actually peppered with blight. These areas suffer shortage of social amenities with respect to acute deficit of clean water supply, improved sanitation, and solid waste management (Mutisya and Yarime, 2011).

Considering the high rates of urban decay in Nairobi (UNEP, 2007), urban renewal is a trend that shall be embraced to restore areas affected by blight. This research is timely as the Government of Kenya is seeking to implement urban renewal strategies in various parts of Nairobi. While the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) advocated for environmental sustainability, the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) go ahead to address specific intricacies pertaining to the urban environment. As such, SDGs aim at making cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable; ensuring the availability and sustainable management of water and sanitation for all; and ending poverty in all its forms everywhere (Umberto *et al.* 2015).

The people of Kenya, as envisaged in the constitution, are respectful of the environment and regard it as the heritage, and always determined to sustain it for the benefit of future generations. Article 42 of the Kenyan constitution further states that, "Every person has the right to a clean and healthy environment, which includes first the right to have the environment protected for the

benefit of present and future generations through legislative and other measures, particularly those contemplated in Article 69; and secondly the right to have obligations relating to the environment fulfilled under Article 70.

Article 70 (1) guarantees clean environment as a claimable right by any member who feels that his rights to a clean environment has been infringed. This article provides that, “If a person alleges that a right to a clean and healthy environment recognized and protected under Article 42 has been, is being or is likely to be, denied, violated, infringed or threatened, the person may apply to a court for redress in addition to any other legal remedies that are available in respect to the same matter (GoK, 2010).

Cities are important sites for engaging with environmental issues (Dodman *et al.* 2013). This is because more than half of the world’s populations live in towns and cities. In regard to this, Kenya’s EMCA 1999 Act of Parliament Assented to in 1999 and commenced in 2000 provides for the establishment of an appropriate legal and institutional framework for appropriate management of the environment and for all matters connected therewith and incidental thereto.

This study is designed to investigate whether urban renewal is an effective tool of environmental management. The results of this study shall be key in making authoritative recommendations on how best this tool can be employed in Kenya and elsewhere to achieve the best results. In regard to this, it shall be effective in quantifying the present day requirements and estimate future needs of populations.

1.4 Aim and Objectives

The overall aim of this research study is to analyze the effectiveness of urban renewal in Nairobi as an urban environmental management strategy.

The specific objectives evolved to actualize this aim are to;

1. Identify the prevailing environmental conditions in selected areas of Nairobi.
2. Identify various urban renewal strategies implemented in Nairobi.
3. Assess the effectiveness of urban renewal strategies as tool for addressing environmental challenges in the selected areas of Nairobi.
4. Evolve credible and actionable recommendations in using Urban Renewal to enhance better management of the environment.

1.5 Research Hypotheses

There is no significant difference in the environment before and after the implementation of Urban Renewal strategies.

1.6 Research Methodology

This section provides a framework under which the study was conducted. It comprises of the target population and samples under consideration, research design, research tools and instruments, data collection and analysis methods. A combination of all these components led to the results upon which conclusions were drawn.

1.6.1 Research Design

The study employed the cross-sectional survey research design using both primary and secondary methods of data collection. Primary data collection specifically entailed the use of Observation and Survey Methods.

Observation method was important for making inferences by the researcher through direct observation of a situation(s) before and after renewal. This was employed while in the areas where the Project Affected Persons used to live previously i.e. in Mukuru and Kibera Informal

settlement before moving into the Relocation Action Plan Units. This was coupled by the use of photo and figures for recording purposes.

A household survey method was conducted through administering structured surveys in form of questionnaires (see Appendix 1) to the sampled households. Unstructured surveys were conducted through the use of Focus Group Discussions with the occupants of the RAP units in a bid to generate more tangent realizations that complement information obtained from the questionnaires (see Appendix 2). Auxiliary, Key Informant Interviews with experts from KRC were conducted to obtain further in-depth information about the RAP project, having been a key implementer and stakeholder of the project (see Appendix 3).

Secondary data was majorly sourced through the use of archival methods.

1.6.2 Target Population

The target population was of approximately 1200 households of Kenya Railways Relocation Plan (KRC, 2015). It is from this population that the study sample was drawn.

1.6.3 Sample Size

The study sought to obtain a sample representation of the target population that has sufficient statistical power (Mugenda and Mugenda, 1999). In calculating the sample size, the study adopted (Fisher, Laing, and Stoeckel, 1983) formula, shown in Equation (1) below to determine the sample size as follows:

$$n = \frac{z^2 pq}{d^2} \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where,

n → desired sample size,

z → standard normal deviation at required confidence level,

d → level of statistical significance level,

p → probability (that an individual has the characteristic being studied),

$$q = 1 - p$$

p → Probability that an individual does not have the characteristic being studied;

The formula (Equation 1) makes a statistical assumption that the selection of households is random and not biased. This study assumed there was a large population of unknown variability in the proportion. Therefore, $p = 0.5$ (maximum variability) was assumed. Additionally, the standard normal deviation at a confidence level of 95% was 1.96 and the level of statistical significance level (precision) $d = \pm 5\%$ was desired. The resulting sample size is demonstrated in the computation below.

$$n = \frac{z^2 pq}{d^2} = \frac{1.96^2 \times 0.5 \times 0.5}{0.05^2} = 384 \text{ Households}$$

1.6.4 Sampling Procedure

First, the study purposively sampled out the case of Relocation Action Plan (RAP) Units Project at Makongeni, Mbotela and Kianda and Soweto areas. This was designed as such because these cases are information-rich, hence would provide a platform for an in-depth analysis for urban renewal and environmental management issues being studied.

Thereafter, probabilistic sampling techniques were employed because they guaranteed samples as a representative of the population (Selltiz, Jahoda, Deutsch, and Cook, 1976). Secondly, cluster sampling technique was used to obtain representative samples from Makongeni, Mbotela and Kianda and Soweto areas.

Finally, systematic random sampling was carried out to select subjects of the study areas. This is usually achieved when the elements of the population are put into a list and then every k^{th} element in the list is chosen (systematically) for inclusion in the sample (Kerlinger and Lee, 1999). To determine the k^{th} element, the total households figure was divided by the total sample households i.e. $\frac{1200}{384}$ to obtain 3.125. The study thus adopted every 3rd element to be the k^{th} element.

1.6.5 Research Instruments

The table below provides a summary of the research instruments used to address the objectives effectively.

Table 1.1 Research Instruments to Address the Research Objectives

Objective	Data	Research Instrument	Tool (s)
1. To identify the prevailing environmental condition and challenges in the select four case areas of Nairobi	Primary and Secondary data	Quantitative and Qualitative Instruments.	Structured Questionnaire, FGDs, Archival methods (Literature, Internet).
2. To assess the effectiveness of the UR strategies in addressing environmental challenges	Primary Data	Quantitative and Qualitative Instruments.	Structured Questionnaire, FGDs, Key Informant Interviews,
3. To identify UR strategies for environmental management implemented in Nairobi,	Secondary Data		Archival Methods
4. To evolve credible and actionable recommendations in using Urban Renewal to enhance better management of the environment.	Primary Data Secondary Data	Quantitative and Qualitative Instruments.	Structured Questionnaire, FGDs, Archival methods (Literature, Internet).

Source; Author, 2016

Quantitative data were gathered using structured questionnaires. These were administered to 384 households sourced from the four clusters of Makongeni, Mbotela and Kianda and Soweto areas.

Qualitative data were sourced by:

Conducting Key Interviews with key informants who were selected officials from the Kenya Railways Corporation (KRC) (see Appendix 3).

Through the use of Focused group discussions (FGDs) with the occupants of The Relocation Action Plan Units in the selected case areas of this study and finally,

By using open ended questions in the questionnaires. This was done as such so as to allow for flexibility and to obtain an in depth view of the subject under study (Sarantakos, 2013). Further, it allows a researcher to understand better, a little known phenomenon (Michael, 2002).

Archival methods were used to complement data obtained from the questionnaires, and generally entailed a review of published books, journals, papers, periodicals government policy documents, environmental standards, sessional papers and media sources. In some cases it was used to complement information obtained from the field.

1.6.6 Pilot Study

A pilot study was conducted before actual data collection was done where a sample of 10 questionnaires were administered within the area adjoining the study areas.

The Procedures used for Conducting the Pilot Study were as follows;

Questionnaires were administered in exactly the same way that they would be administered in the actual data collection;

A record of all the ambiguities and difficulties that the respondents were facing were put down;

A record of the time taken to complete the questionnaire was also recorded to determine whether time taken was reasonable; and finally an

Assessment on whether every question could give an adequate range of responses was done.

The outcomes of the pilot study necessitated that the questionnaires were shortened and revised further so as to save on time during the actual data collection, and all the unnecessary difficult and ambiguous questions discarded. There was provision for adequate range of responses for

some of the questions, and a revision of the interview schedules was carried out so as to gather more appropriate information that was relevant to the study was carried out.

This proved well to evaluate the effectiveness of the questionnaires. It created a basis for making questionnaires better understood by clarifying the instructions and simplifying the language to ensure that correct interpretations are made.

1.6.6.1 Testing of Research Instruments based on the Pilot Survey

For maximum validity of the instrument, questions in the questionnaire were reconstructed in consultation with the supervisor to ensure that all key areas of the study were addressed. This helped to reduce biases before data collection. Opinions were sought from lecturers in the department and several environmental experts in Kenya to examine the validity of the research instrument used.

This research employed the test-retest technique to ensure reliability of the questionnaires. First a sample of 10 questionnaires was administered occupants to respondents. The same questionnaires were re-administered to the same respondents after a span of two weeks. The scores from both tests were correlated to determine the coefficient of reliability using the Karl Pearson’s Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation (r) (see Equation 2). The items were scored individually and aggregated to get the total score on the whole instrument for both test and pre-test administrations.

$$r = \frac{n \sum xy - \sum x \sum y}{\sqrt{\{n \sum x^2 - (\sum x)^2\} \{n \sum y^2 - (\sum y)^2\}}} \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Where

- r = Reliability coefficient,
- n = Number of respondents,
- $\sum xy$ = Sum of the products of paired scores
- $\sum x$ = Sum of x Scores
- $\sum y$ = Sum of y Scores
- $\sum x^2$ = Sum of squared x Scores
- $\sum y^2$ = Sum of squared y Scores

1.7 Context of the Study

1.7.1 Profile of Nairobi and an Overview of the Study Area

Nairobi is the capital and largest city of Kenya. The city and its surrounding area also form the Nairobi County. The name "Nairobi" comes from the Maasai phrase 'Enkare Nyrobi', which translates to "cool water". The area was originally grazing land and a livestock watering point and there was no permanent African settlement.

The city of Nairobi owes its early development and growth to the Kenya Uganda Railway. The railhead reached Nairobi in June 1899 and by July 1899 it had become the headquarters of the Kenya Uganda Railway (Rakodi, 1997). This led to Nairobi's growth as a commercial and business hub of the British East Africa protectorate (Mitullah, 2003). By 1900, Nairobi had become a large and flourishing place with the settlement consisting mainly of the railway buildings and separate areas for Europeans and Indians, the latter mainly comprising the labourers engaged in building the railway. Nairobi, as an urban centre was officially defined in 1900 under the Nairobi Municipal Community regulations and it became the capital of Kenya in 1907 (Mitullah, 2003; Rakodi, 1997).

Nairobi was previously known as 'the city in the sun' because of its appealing environment. It has a total area of 696.1 Km² and is located between coordinates 1°09' South 36°39' East and 1°27' South 37°06' East. It lies at an altitude of 1,798 meters above sea level (NCC, 2014).

Figure 1.1 Location of the City of Nairobi

Source: UNEP (2009); KNBS (2014)

Nairobi’s physical and topographic features include rivers, plains, vegetation and forests. There are three forests in the Nairobi i.e. Ngong Forest (to the south), Karura Forest (to the north) and the Nairobi Arboretum. These three forests have a total coverage of 23.19 km². The terrain in the eastern side of the city is gently rolling but divided by steep valleys towards the city. The Karen - Langata area is characterized by plains surrounded by Nairobi National Park on the east and Ngong Forest on the south. Several streams with steep-sided valleys covered with vegetation are a dominant landscape feature of the city. The main rivers in Nairobi are Nairobi River, Ngong River and Kabuthi River. These rivers are highly polluted as open sewers and industrial waste is directed towards them. Nairobi dam, which is along the Ngong River, and Jamhuri dam are the main water reservoirs in Nairobi (NCC, 2014).

Nairobi is currently home to nearly four million people and represents about a quarter of Kenya's urban population. The Kenya population census and Nairobi City population projections are as shown in Table 1.2 and Table 1.3.

Table 1.2 Population trends (census) in Kenya and Nairobi

Year	Nairobi's Population	Increase in Population	Area (km²)	Density (People per km²)	Kenya's Population	Nairobi as % of Kenya Population
1906	11,512	-	18.13	635	n/a	-
1928	29,864	159.4	25.37	1,177	n/a	-
1931	47,919	60.5	25.37	1,889	3,073,947	1.6
1962	343,500	124.2	684	390	8,636,263	3.1
1969	509,286	90.9	684	745	10,942,705	4.7
1979	827,775	62.5	684	1,210	15,327,000	5.4
1989	1,324,570	60.0	696	1,937	21,445,000	6.2
1999	2,143,254	61.8	696	3,079	28,686,607	7.5
2009	3,138,369	46.4	696.1	4,509	38,610,097	8.1

Source: Olima (2001) and KNBS (2010)

Table 1.3 Population Projections in Nairobi

Year	2000	2012	2015	2017	2020	2025
Nairobi	2,233,000	3,517,325	3,942,054	4,253,330	4,881,000	5,871,000

Source; (KNBS, 2010)

The gradual population dynamics of Nairobi evidently typifies it as the most rapidly urbanizing city in sub-Saharan Africa. According to NEMA (2003), Nairobi's early growth was fueled by rural immigrants, and an explosion of growth took place between 1979 and 1989. The forces motivating rural-urban migration to Nairobi include better economic prospects, opportunities for higher education and higher wage employment, and the attraction of Nairobi as a market for goods and services (UNEP, 2009).

As the capital and largest city of Kenya, Nairobi has always been the major attraction of various segments of the Kenyan population—from rural and other urban areas—in search of better livelihood opportunities. As such, a growing economy and swelling population numbers from both in-migration and natural growth are continually increasing the city's size. A significant

number of commuters from satellite towns such as Naivasha, Machakos, Ngong, and Thika come into Nairobi daily to work or bring goods and supplies contributing to an estimated additional half-million people to the city's population.

The consequence of rapid and uncontrolled population explosion in Nairobi is the proliferation of informal settlements that serves as the main force driving the city's overwhelming environmental challenges (APHRC, 2012; UNEP, 2009). Ongoing rural to urban migration, high natural birth rates, and poor or inappropriate city planning conspire to continue degrading the city's environment. In turn, environmental degradation has had impacts on human health and the economy. For the country to achieve the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs), progress must be made in Nairobi, as Kenya's capital city and its largest urban centre (UNEP, 2009).

The informal settlements in Nairobi are the most populated hosting 29% of the city's population, most of who experience poor access to basic infrastructure services. Besides, Nairobi also has the largest slum in East and Central Africa, that is Kibera; and others such as Kawangware, Mathare, Kangemi, Korogocho, Majengo, Kitui Village and Kiambiu (NCC, 2014). Meeting the increasing demand of this new population is a daunting challenge for policy makers and, specifically, for Nairobi authorities (APHRC, 2012).

The number of slums is increasing due to housing problems and many families are entering the food poverty bracket (NCC, 2014). According to Shihembetsa (1989), it's the Government of Kenya (GoK) that essentially allowed these shacks to be built within the city as long as they were not located within the Central Business District (CBD). The Nairobi informal settlements are owned by the Nairobi County, Private landlords and other precarious people who, as identified by Mitullah (2002) depend largely on influential persons to protect their right of ownership to the land.

Nairobi's informal settlements, though classified as illegal, continue to exist since independence to date (Mutisya and Yarime, 2011). Slum dwellers in these marginalized areas live under deplorable conditions lacking the most basic needs and social amenities. These residents suffer a severe lack of clean water supply, improper sanitation, challenges of housing, poor health services, lack of solid waste management facilities, improper drainage systems, high crime rates, and lack of proper governance and high insecurity services. This has resulted to life threatening

outcomes which lead to mass poverty, contagious diseases, conflicts, and other social, ecological and economic hazards (Situma, 1992; Olima, 2001; UN, 2006; COHRE, 2008).

In a bid to provide decent and affordable housing for the target group and rationalize and optimize economic use of prime land in city, Nairobi county has recently embarked on various urban renewal projects in; Mbotela, Shauri moyo, Ziwani, Mbotela, Makongeni, Gorofani, Starehe, Ofafa kunguni, Jericho, Jerusalem Maringo, Old and New Ngara and Jevanjee as well as Kibera (NCC, 2014). This study therefore examines the effectiveness of these projects on environmental management.

1.7.2 Case Study Areas:

This research picked up the case of Relocation Action Plan (RAP) units by Kenya Railways Corporation, Ministry of Transport and Infrastructure, and World Bank at Makongeni, Mbotela, Kianda and Soweto areas.

1.7.2.1 Brief History and Overview of RAP units

The project began in 2004-2005 because the Kenya Railway Reserve, approximately 30 metres on both sides of the railway line except at the station yards and the major depots, had been heavily encroached by slum residents in Mukuru and Kibera settlements (See scope of project in Appendix 4 figures A, B1, B2 and B3).

These residents had built their shacks right next to the railway road, even turning the railway corridor to a garbage disposal area. According to Longinus (2010), the whole encroached stretch had become a safety threat not only to the train operations but to the residents themselves. Further, it had become increasingly unhygienic, very difficult to maintain, compromising on the track drainage and stability as well. As a result, incidences and accidents along the railway corridor had led to the claiming lives in these densely populated areas. Trains had been forced to reduce their speed, given the physical challenges that prevailed in these regions, greatly impacting on the Rift Valley Railways (RVR) company in terms of incurring huge losses.

As a result of this, an eviction threat was released for all encroachers of the 60 metres reserve to vacate the premises. The aftermath of this threat foresaw many interventions by different groups including The Slum Dwellers International (SDI) together with its affiliate federation in Kenya

Muungano wa Wanavijiji, and support NGO Pamoja Trust that were against the looming evictions. SDI intervention led to a court injunction that stopped the KRC's eviction intentions and created a platform for discussion with the KRC. According to SDI, sustainable development programs and sufficient investments resources had to be put in place so as to enable these affected persons to reinstate their lives to the original, pre-displacement livelihoods levels or even higher (KRC, 2015).

An exchange visit to India was thus scheduled and effected by SDI for a Kenyan federation of key stakeholders to learn about a similar case study in Mumbai where railway slum dwellers had been resettled. As a result, the KRC thus consented and ceded 5.2 metres on either sides of the railway reserve for the creation of resettlement units. The first enumeration programme of residents on the 5.2 metre gauge was effected in 2005. The rest of the dwellers on the remaining 25 metres had to vacate and get new dwellings.

After this, not much happened on the project until 2010 where KRC together with World Bank embarked on the project. So much had happened by then including increased encroachment, vertical and horizontal densification of households, uprooting of railway tracks by angry Kibera Citizens during the 2007 Post election violence period, derailment anxiety after the train accident in December 2009, increased use of corridor as a dumping site for wastes, and the increased use of the railway corridor by various institutions in Mukuru settlement (Weru, 2011).

A new enumeration was thus necessary, and was conducted in 2010, mapping all the residential, business, and institutional land uses within the 60 metre KRC reserve (see Figure 1.2 below).

Figure 1.2 Image Digitization of the Encroached 60m-Wide Railway Reserve.

Source: RAP Files, 2014

This latter enumeration further aimed at achieving an extended safety corridor for railway operations and maintenance, to act as a buffer zone to minimize danger posed by accidents or derailments. Besides this it entailed erecting a heightened wall to secure the railway corridor against future encroachment; and providing footpath and overhead alternatives for human traffic away from the railway reserve (Weru, 2011).

The residential houses in detail entail a single room house that measure 4.5 metres by 4.2 metres and comprise of a kitchen, a sleeping area and a toilet whereas business stalls are each approximately 1.5 meters by 2.5 metres. In total all units shall be 10000 in number upon completion. Currently, 1200 households from the slum have moved into the new houses located in Makongeni, Mbotela, Soweto East and Kianda Areas. Apart from these residential structures, Kenya Railways is set to put up public schools and churches to benefit the new occupants.

Figure 1.3 Residential Floor Plan

Source: RAP Files, 2014

Figure 1.4 Business Stall Floor Plan,

Source: RAP Files, 2014

Figure 1.5 Makongeni and Mbotela Segment

Source; RAP Files, 2014

LEGEND

- Residential Units
- Boundary Wall
- Business stalls
- Railway Line

Figure 1.6 Kianda and Soweto Area

Source; RAP Files, 2014

CHAPTER TWO

2. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK AND LITERATURE REVIEW

The conceptual and theoretical frameworks provided in this dissertation are only meant to establish orderly connections between observations and facts. Further, besides these frameworks embodying the direction to which the research will have to be undertaken, these stimulate the extension of knowledge by providing direction and impetus.

2.1 Theoretical Framework

Several theories and models have been used to contribute to studies done in Urban Planning field. An example of this is the Growth machine theory by Harvey Molotch in 1976. According to this theory, the city is a growth machine. Molotch (1976) reversed the arguments of the Urban Theory pointing out that cities' lands were not just empty parcels awaiting human action but were attached to particular interests commercial, sentimental or psychological. Urban growth is driven by a coalition of interest groups who all benefit from continuous growth and expansion. The outcome, the shape of cities and the distribution of their peoples, is thus not due to an interpersonal market or geographic necessities, but due to social actions, including opportunistic dealings. As such, cities should be studied in terms of its organisations and activities generally (Molotch, 1976).

Another theory is the broken windows theory which argues that the landscape of an area potentially communicates i.e. little indicators of neglect, such as unmaintained building's portions such as broken windows and unkempt lawns, encourage a feeling that an area is in a state of decay. On the other hand, a well ordered and clean environment psychologically implies that an area is monitored and managed (Boundless, 2016). To counter urban decay, cities launch urban renewal strategies and programs.

The theory of sustainable development emphasizes that all forms of development ought to be sustainable. It elaborates on the process of meeting human development goals while maintaining the ability of natural systems to continue to provide natural resources and ecosystem services upon which the community depends. It is the organizing principle and theory for sustaining finite resources necessary to provide for the needs of future generations of life. It is a process that

envisioning a desirable future state for human societies in which living conditions and resource-use continue to meet human needs without undermining the integrity, stability and beauty of the environment.

Despite the wide range of these theories that could be successfully be used, this dissertation adopts the Stern's value-belief-norm (VBN) theory of environmentalism which suggests that bearing and perceiving adverse effects from a certain environmental challenge could promote mitigation behaviour. The VBN theory of environmentalism postulates a causal chain of five variables: values, the New Environmental (or Ecological) Paradigm (NEP), awareness of consequences (AC), ascription of responsibility (AR) to self-beliefs concerning the biophysical environment, and personal norms (PN) for pro-environmental actions.

Illustration of The VBN Trend adapted from Stern (2000)

According to Stern (2000), the above causal chain moves from relatively stable elements that an individual draws from the environment (Biospheric, Altruistic, Egoistic values) to central elements of personality and beliefs and finally to more focused beliefs about human environments relations, the consequences of these relations and the responsibility of the individual to take corrective action.

Each variable affects the next in the chain directly, and further affects directly other variables in the chain. Normatively, a sense of obligation to take proenvironmental actions (PN) or to display

environmentally significant behavior is affected by an individual's belief element. The belief is that environmental conditions put to threat, an individual's value and hence the individual is forced to interpose to reduce the threat.

This study seeks to evaluate how the elements of Value, Belief and Personal Norms towards the environment are revealed, or rather manifest themselves in urban development and in this case in Urban Renewal activities in Nairobi, and their relative importance.

As such, this study implored into this theory in an explanatory-wise manner so as to explain and specify certain relations, dimensions or characteristics where certain considerations in this case variables, were put in place. In this study, correlations were done to infer the difference between the past situation and the present/current situation of the sample population in the study area. In a nutshell, this theory was used to depict whether the implementers of the Kenya Railway Relocation Units had values and beliefs accrued towards the care/protection/management of the ecological system (pro-environmental actions) while putting up efforts in fighting decay.

2.2 Conceptual Framework

Figure 2.1 Conceptual Framework

Source; Author, 2016

2.3 Concept of Environmental Management

2.3.1 Definition of environmental management

The term *environment* refers to the surroundings in which an organization operates, including air, water, land, natural resources, flora, fauna, humans and their interrelationships (ISO 14001, 2015). Environmental management is a systematic and orderly process in which organizations apply mechanisms to develop, maintain or improve of the ambient quality of the environment (Lovei and Weiss, 1998). Environmental management focuses on the improvement of human welfare for present and future generations.

An environmental management system (EMS) refers to a collection of activities undertaken to manage environmental aspects, fulfil compliance obligations and address risk opportunities. Environmental aspects include activities or products or services that interact or can interact with the environment (ISO 14001, 2015). An environmental aspect can cause (an) environmental impact(s). An EMS is important for: Consistently complying with environmental laws; Improving overall environmental performance; Addressing environmental liability from current or past practices; Maximizing investment in environmental affairs; Integration of environmental objectives into overall mission and business objectives; and Providing an environmentally safe workplace etc (ISO 14001, 2015). While the ultimate objective of environmental management is to protect or improve environmental conditions, the purpose of environmental management, is either: To reduce negative (or enhance positive) environmental externalities; To provide environmentally related public goods; To improve sectoral or spatial natural resource allocation between productive, consumptive and non-consumptive uses to control environmental degradation; and/or To reallocate natural goods and services across time for successive generations (Jan, Pieter, Willem, and Bart, 2001).

2.3.2 Environmental Management Infrastructure in Kenya

The National Environment Management Authority (NEMA) [established under the Environmental Management and Coordination Act (EMCA) No. 8 of 1999], is the principal instrument of government of Kenya in the implementation of all environmental policies (EMCA, 1999). This Act establishes national environmental principles and provides guidance and

coherence to good environmental management. EMCA (1999) deals with issues that cut across all sectors such as: environmental policy, environmental planning, protection and conservation of the environment, environmental impact assessment, environmental audit and monitoring, environmental quality standards, environmental protection orders, environmental inspection, institutional coordination and conflict resolution. To enhance proper environmental management at the regional levels, EMCA under section 30 has established District Environment Committees (DECs) and the Provincial Environment Committees (PECs).

This study delves into how Urban Renewal strategies have been implemented in Nairobi, and how these consider the well-being of the environment. To obtain a thorough grasp on this topic the report attempts to discuss the nexus between Urban Renewal and Environment Management.

2.4 Concept of Urban Renewal

Urban renewal (UR) refers to the diversified efforts to eliminate and prevent slums and blight, whether residential or non-residential, and the removal of the factors that create such slums and blighting conditions (Colborn, 1963). It also refers to a deliberate attempt to change the environment of urban areas so as to meet the present and the future needs of a living and working society (Grebler, 1964). Agbola (1987) envisions urban renewal as a relatively comprehensive community redevelopment programme through which a particular city seeks to refashion and rebuild the physical structure of a particular segment(s) in order to enable it cope successfully with the emerging problems confronting it. Such segments have a common characteristic such as poorly constructed buildings, faulty planning, lacking/inadequate open spaces, deteriorated properties, having an incompatible mix of uses and improper utilization of land (Aluko and Amidu, 2006).

The process of urban renewal may involve an extensive demolition of property, most of it old, in a way that clears a large area of ground thus permitting the planning and reconstruction of a new set of buildings, streets and space(s) (Medhurst and Parry, 1969). Consequently it rebuilds the image of the city, conserving and creating a new urban environment with aesthetically pleasing physical environment while considering the economic base (Agbola, 1987).

Urban renewal has been considered to be a sound approach that promotes land values and enhance the environmental quality (Adams and Hastings, 2001); rectify the problem of urban decay and meet several socioeconomic objectives (Lee and Chan, 2008); improve existing social networks, enhance the inclusion of vulnerable groups, and manage adverse environmental impacts (Chan and Yung, 2008). This has subsequently called into play various urban renewal strategies in various settings of the world.

2.4.1 Urban Renewal Strategies

The main approaches of urban renewal include redevelopment, rehabilitation and conservation (of monuments), spot clearance and revitalization (Broudehau, 1994; Egunjobi, 1997; Shinn, 1987). This section examines the aforementioned strategies.

2.4.1.1 Urban Redevelopment

This strategy may deploy clearance of existing structures to pave way for redevelopment, and in such case(s) the ‘bulldozer approach’ has often been used (Anderson, 1964). Urban redevelopment is a strategy that has been employed throughout history. It is appreciably dominant where the buildings have massively been cleared or destroyed, for instance, due to wars and natural calamities such as earthquakes, tsunami etc. (Couch, 1990) (Nelson, 1988).

It also entails the implementing of new projects in place of existing building stock that are in seriously deteriorated condition with no preservation value (Miller, 1959). These may include predated traditional structures that are neither healthy nor safe for human habitation (Oduola, 1987). Such structures are often evident in slums, road reserves or areas (earmarked for some development) but not yet developed etc.

2.4.1.2 Rehabilitation.

Rehabilitation refers to the upgrading of substandard structures to standard structures. The former would be due to neglect, lack of maintenance and poor handling techniques (Oduola, 1987). Upgrading of these structures entail repairing and refurbishment. In the long run, the buildings and the neighborhoods at large remain intact (Lichfield, 1998).

Other rehabilitation strategies could include; selling the buildings to private individuals who can be encouraged or induced to rehabilitate such buildings with the aid of various administrative financial and other arrangements; putting sanctions against people who refuse to rehabilitate their own buildings; and applying administrative and financial inducements to private property owners on public or corporaton housing estates and lands (Oduola, 1987).

2.4.1.3 Spot Clearance

Clearance activities are usually related to demolishing structures or preparing a site for development. An example of this would be the demolition of a dilapidated structure(s) in a residential neighborhood from the site on which a development project such as housing /infrastructural facilities will be built. The following clearance activities are eligible: demolition of buildings and improvements; removal of demolition products, rubble, and other debris; physical removal of environmental contaminants or treatment of such contaminants to render them harmless; and movement of structures to other sites. HUD (2012) qualifies clearance on the basis of the following objectives:

Clearance may qualify under the Area Benefit category if the cleared property will be used for a purpose that benefits the residents of a primarily residential area and at least 51% of those residents are primary residents.

Clearance may qualify under the Limited Clientele category if the cleared property will be used for an activity that benefits a specific group of people, at least 51% of whom are primary residents.

Clearance may qualify under the Housing category if the cleared property will be used for housing to be occupied by primary residents.

If the cleared property is part of an activity that will create or retain permanent jobs and at least 51% of those jobs will benefit primary residents, the acquisition may qualify under the Jobs category.

Clearance may qualify under the Slum or Blighted Area category if the clearance activities are in an area designated by the grantee as a slum or blighted area and address one or more of the conditions which contributed to the deterioration of the area.

Clearance may qualify under the Spot Blight category if the activity eliminates specific conditions of blight or physical decay on a spot basis not located in a designated slum/blight area.

Finally, clearance may qualify under the Urban Renewal Completion category if the activities are located within an urban renewal project area or a Neighborhood Development Program action area designated under the Housing Act (of country or local authority) and the clearance is necessary to complete the Urban Renewal Plan.

2.4.1.4 Conservation

The preservation and restoration of publicly and privately owned properties of historical significance (Egunjobi, 1997). Historic properties are those sites or structures which are: Listed or eligible to be listed in the National Register of Historic Places; Listed in a State or local inventory of historic places; or Designated as a State or local landmark or historic district by appropriate law or ordinance (HUD, 2012).

The National Museums and Heritage (Cap. 216) of the Laws of Kenya, for instance, established a detailed list of procedures for actions involving historic structures/sites of national heritage (GoK, 2009). Prior to conducting any type of historic preservation activities, the project implementing agency should ensure compliance with this Act and other relevant statutes.

Different urban renewal strategies implemented are based on specific issue to be solved i.e. strategies must be problem oriented and not blanket type (Oduola, 1987). The growing trend of modern urban renewal activities in the world cities has however immensely influenced and impacted on urban environmental settings in various ways.

2.5 Literature Review

Cities are the places to be these days, which mean big changes for the historic communities that have populated urban cores. Thus, the world is experiencing a new and dynamic wave of urban renewal and a quest for effective environmental management there to is thus inevitable. This section gives an exposition into urban renewal and strategies that have been deployed therein, and various mileages that have been experienced and how they impact their respective environments.

This section delves into the literature review on Urban Renewal and Environmental Management and converses the nexus thereof. It gives a global scenario of this subject at hand, narrowing down to African's experience and finally Kenya with a focus on Nairobi, as the choice study area of this research. Most importantly, this literature review discusses the 'what was the case before the implementation of the UR strategies', and the 'what was the case after implementation'. This shall be as well important while addressing the 'what it will be like if this research's recommendations are considered' in the conclusion of this dissertation. Importantly, these questions were used to identify the extent and the existing gaps in knowledge on UR.

2.5.1 Urban Renewal and Environmental Management in America

The first major urban renewal efforts in the United States came up in response to environmental degradation as a result of mix due to urbanization and industrialization (Holcomb and Beauregard, 1981). This program was geared by The Public Works and Public Housing Department in the late 19th Century. The most profound of these were the cases of American Park movement and the City Beautiful movement. The movements encompassed transforming urban centers by creating urban parks and the constructing monumental public buildings.

In the 1930s, the blight situation and deterioration was accelerated by great economic depression characterized by poverty and high levels of unemployment. Large scale urbanization among other many factors resulted to massive urban decay, development of better and efficient transport systems (railway and increase in car ownership) and development of suburbs. Migration from the cities to the suburbs led to the accumulation of many vacant housing units in the cities that with time deteriorated. Such areas, according to the same author, exhibited health and safety

problems and reflected the 'poor conditions of the labour class after the industrialization process' (Roberts, P. and Sykes, H., 2000).

Renewal strategies at this time thus focused on transforming those abandoned areas into standard habitable areas. Interventions therefore entailed the removal of slums and blighted conditions by demolishing old buildings and constructing new ones in their stead that are of low-income housing, in the form of multistoried apartment complexes (Nelson, 1988).

The first comprehensive move of the U.S federal government towards urban renewal came with the Housing Act of 1949 (Colborn, 1963). The Renewal Program had three main elements i.e. Slum prevention through neighborhood conservation and housing code enforcement; Rehabilitation of structures and neighborhoods; and clearance and redevelopment of structures and neighborhoods (Colborn, 1963).

However, private investors were reluctant to participate because of the restrictions which oriented projects towards housing, not the most lucrative investment in the long run, and because projects took many years to complete, tying up capital for long periods. As a result, urban renewal still consisted mainly of slum clearance and redevelopment.

The criticisms of the Urban Renewal Program were many and as such the program earned the reputation of being a "bulldozer approach", demolishing blighted areas to make room for luxury housing (Santiago, 1975). According to Michael Anderson, author of the *Federal Bulldozer 1964*, its application led to the destruction of more homes than were built, these homes were low rent. Housing conditions were made worse for those whose housing conditions were good and improved for those whose housing conditions were worst and led to the displacement of small businesses (Anderson, 1964).

In 1954 the program was revised to make profits, not the improvement of slums, the primary goal. As such, Slums and areas affected with blight that were adjacent to existing CBDs were cleared and replaced with new land uses for a new class of people, making urban renewal more attractive to private investors (Holcomb and Beauregard, 1981). As the human, social, and economic costs of clearance were slowly recognized, program funds gradually shifted to support rehabilitation more than demolition and reconstruction (Nelson, 1988).

The 1960s brought a gradual acknowledgment that spreading suburbanization would exacerbate city problems and that improving urban conditions required more than physical renewal (Nelson, 1988). As such, Small-scale programs were encouraged, and efforts for example The Model Cities program initiated in 1966, shifted its focus to not only provide housing through physical rebuilding but also pay greater attention to social renewal. Low-income residents were to be organized in order to plan for the physical, economic, and social rehabilitation of their own neighborhoods (Holcomb and Beauregard, 1981).

Urban Revitalization emerged in the 1970s as the dominant approach to urban renewal. By emphasizing neighborhood preservation and housing rehabilitation, it limited displacement and disruption of communities (Holcomb and Beauregard, 1981). Today, housing rehabilitation is increasingly becoming the dominant activity of urban renewal in the United States.

In Europe, the evolution of renewal policies followed a similar pattern as the United States although it had to proceed without the benefit of national programs specifically designed to assist in the process.

2.5.2 Urban Renewal and Environmental Management in Europe

According to Grebler (1964), the need to modernize old city centers initiated during the industrial revolution came later to Europe than to the United States. As a result, European countries have often looked at the American experience as a model for urban renewal. According to Mutlu (2009), there was an outburst of industrial activity in Europe that led to massive construction of industrial buildings and houses to house employment seekers and the working populations. It is in fact recorded that Cities grew outwardly (Couch, 1990). Until 1860s the state's involvement in urban development and renewal process was minimal.

Projects, though minimal, largely entailed the replacement of old houses, and was initiated by investors and the residents. This trend followed until William Torrens in 1868 introduced a bill that sought permission for local governments to clear slummed streets and redevelop them. However later on, the clause on the replacement of old dilapidated buildings and the insanitary areas was dropped providing for the clearance of individual buildings. As such, the legislation encouraged demolition of housing without a relocation policy thus increasing overcrowding

(Gaudie, 1974). Couch 1990 posits that despite its flaws and limited impacts, the legislation made a significant entry of state involvement in urban renewal and development (Karanja, 2014).

War damaged cities after the World war II were left in a run-down state (Couch, 1990). As a result, population suffered serious shortage of housing. In response to this, massive renewal activities according to Grebler (1964) were done. This is seen as ‘the most extensive process of urban renewal in history’ that happened in the 1920s with an emphasized focus on the housing stock (Karanja, 2014). Renewal policies involved scrapping off the unsanitary and unhygienic conditions in working-class neighborhoods through slum clearance and demolition of declining areas (Couch, 1990). According to Couch (1964) and Broudehoux (1964), this specific phase encountered challenges including the;

Demolition of structurally sound buildings which with some renovation could provide housing;

Demolition of natural habitats, historical landscapes and architectural heritage which elicited opposition from conservation movements who advocated for preservation;

Dissatisfaction from the relocated families due to loss of social ties;

Insensitive process of relocation and

The poor quality of the buildings they were rehoused in.

Legislations on renewal practices were formulated to indicate the role of local authorities, the implementation stages as well as financing of the solutions (Couch, 1990).

Renewal programs were reoriented after 1950s, adapting rehabilitation of the existing stock and area improvement (Couch, 1990). Today, in the western world, most urban renewal actions are based on residential rehabilitation and upgrading (Karanja, 2014).

2.5.3 Urban Renewal and Environmental Management in Asia

Major renewal programs in Asia have taken place in Hong Kong and Singapore through public private partnerships. Renewal efforts entailed large scale slum clearance schemes, inner city renewal, and redevelopment of public housing estates (Williams, 1979).

The first renewal scheme by the public in Hong Kong came about in 1954 after the disastrous Shek Kip Mei fire that resulted to 53,000 squatters of this overly congested area homeless (Castells, 1990). The scheme entailed resettling the squatters to public housing estates/ temporal houses.

In 1972, redevelopment of these resettlement estates was introduced. Williams (1979) posits that the previous housing blocks were demolished and new blocks were put up instead and others converted into self-contained units, modern schools and recreational facilities. In 1974, in-situ redevelopment of dilapidated properties in old inner city-districts was introduced. In this scheme newly constructed buildings i.e. apartments, were sold to the families that were living on the renewal sites at relatively low prices, which helped to avoid social disruption (Yeh, 1990).

By 1987, The Land Development Corporation (LDC) was mandated to carry out Redevelopment activities in Hong Kong by using resources from the private sector. This was in a bid to achieve several goals that include speeding up the private sector redevelopment in selected areas, encouraging the participation of landowners, improving the quality and economic benefit of development by assembling larger sites, ensuring an equitable treatment of the tenants, and to minimize government subsidies (HKHA, 1988). The LDC acquired some units near the redevelopment sites and the tenants were rehoused whereas others who are most affected were offered mortgages at low interest rates for them to buy new homes.

In Singapore, urban renewal programs were initiated as early as 1960s and followed almost the same trend as in Hong Kong, most of it being carried out in the inner-city areas through public private partnerships. In 1964, the Urban Renewal Program for the Central China Town was launched, with the aid of foreign consultants (Lim, 1983). Through this, the state acquired lands, pooled them together and then released them to the private sector on a competitive basis for development (Mann, 1984).

Policies in Asia had that no demolitions would be effected if alternative housing for squatters had not been acquired. Businessmen were also compensated and given incentives to start up again their businesses in the new housing estates (Siew-Eng, 1989). Urban Renewal Program resulted to the redevelopment of all colonial neighborhoods, basically two- and three-story century-old shop houses, and in the relocation of all original residents and businesses.

Today, the central area has been completely redeveloped with shopping complexes, office towers, and apartment blocks, and the new high-rise Singapore has replaced the former colonial city. Only a few affluent colonial residential areas have been preserved (Broudehoux A. , 1994). Considerable emphasis has recently been placed upon upgrading the physical environment of old inner-city neighborhoods (Castells, 1990).

2.5.4 Urban Renewal and Environmental Management in Africa

This section looks at an in depth view of Urban Renewal and Environmental Management at depth in Developing countries.

According to Broudehoux (1994), in developing countries, the process of urban renewal is still relatively new. Besides this, renewal efforts seem to concentrate on solving the problems of urban slums, in which 30 to 60% of the urban population resides and are considered the fastest growing portion of Third World cities.

In the late 1970s, Governments began realizing the socio-economic impacts of slum demolition. Slum and squatter upgrading and sites and services, replaced the previous clearance policies (Schmit-Kallert, 1990). Of importance to note is that substandard housing, including squatter shanties, was recognized as part of the housing stock. Community upgrading appeared as a general way to improve the living conditions in the informal settlements (Laquian, 1983). This was adopted as an official policy in the 1980s (Van, 1982). Provision of infrastructure and basic services including the legalization of land tenure took lead during this era.

Basic services were introduced on the sites and house improvement works were undertaken by the residents themselves (Laquian, 1983). Settlements were upgraded by improving the infrastructure and legalizing land tenure. Today, upgrading remains the most sensible approach to resolving the problems of informal settlements in Third World cities, although clearance is still commonly used (Faerstein, 1989).

In summary, it can be observed that, both in developing and developed countries, the evolution of policies pertaining UR followed similar patterns, evolving gradually from a demolition and reconstruction approach to a softer, more socially and psychologically-oriented approach, that concentrates on the renovation of existing structures.

Better still, this report selects relevant case examples from Africa apart from Kenya including, Nigeria, and S. Africa in Africa that form the two biggest economies of Africa. These two countries coincidentally have done/ are doing rampant Urban Renewal exercises in their cities and thus build a good case for this study. It then finalizes with Kenya wherewith the report discusses the country's history which majorly informs its urban renewal efforts and programs.

2.5.4.1 Nigerian Experience

In Nigeria, Urban Renewal (UR) is being implemented in many towns though poverty coupled by high urbanization rates militate against these developments. In Nigeria, UR has always taken the approach of slum housing demolition and a consequent construction of better and more costly ones. Of course this has led to the displacement and eviction of the low-income class people due to increased rental rates. As such, to date environmental impact assessment on urban renewal areas are done so as to take an account of the original residents and their environment. (Njoku and Okoro, 2014)

Profound examples of renewal carried out in Nigeria are the 1988 Ndoki and 1991 Aggrey Road Water Front in Rivers State which were undertaken by The Rivers State Land and Housing Bureau (RSLHB), and the Maroko- Lagos and Aja experiment, in Lagos State. In both projects eviction resulted to large-scale relocation of families and individuals with no compensation. They were promised to be given priority on completion of the dwelling units. It is recorded that at the end, 27.3 percent of the new residents were of low-income group, while the rest 72.7 percent belong to the medium and high-income groups (Ibeakuzie, 2002).

According to Kingsley and Omatone (2010), renewal schemes generally brought about the revitalization of the urban environment. Despite of this, evidently, the renewal scheme did not really solve the problem of housing but rather caused more problems including; Break-up of social structures, an upset in the existing economic systems and opportunities, a compounding of the congestion in Port Harcourt infrastructure due to migration of displaced squatters and an expanding and increment of the number of marginal water front squatter settlements or expansion/creation of other informal settlements elsewhere in the city.

The cases of Maroko and Aja villages in Lagos have been termed to be of no difference. In July 1990 squatters residing at Maroko faced the Lagos State bulldozer while the same was implemented in 1995 in Aja village (Kingsley and Omatson, 2010).

Recently, UR projects in Osun have been evaluated and appraised so as to ensure that environmental sustainability is achieved. It is no doubt that the urban environment shall rejuvenate, and possibly have a spread effect on the neighboring environs of selected states. SWOT analysis carried out highlights the positive effects of the programme, even environmental sustainability measures. Of importance to note is that issues such as improving the quality of the environment, the aesthetics, protection of flora and fauna and proper management of solid waste have been highlighted. Despite of this, issues of the poor involvement of the residents in the implementation plan, poor sensitization of the Osun State populace, lack of political will, corruption in governance and lack of project continuity remain a challenge of implementing these projects (Adiabokpa, 2012).

2.5.4.2 South African Experience

Urban renewal programme in South Africa was instituted in 1999 by President Thabo and began being implemented in 2001 as a tool through which the government together with private partners can address the challenges facing the country.

Urban Renewal Programme focuses on eight urban townships also referred to as the countries' "urban nodes". These nodes include Alexandra in the City of Johannesburg, Mitchell's Plain and Khayelitsha in the City of Cape Town, Inanda and KwaMahu (INK) in the Thekwini Municipality, Mdantsane in the Buffalo City Municipality (East London), Motherwell in the Nelson Mandela Bay (Port Elizabeth) and Galeshewe in the Sol Plaatje Municipality.

It largely entails the revitalization of strategic urban localities through refurbishing of infrastructure, Local Economic Development projects and social integration. More to this, it encompasses the creation of human settlements and the provision of livelihood opportunities to make townships a place where people are attracted to live, work and invest (Suzan, 2010).

Some of the common "characteristic features" of the selected Urban Renewal nodes are that they are apartheid townships, characterized by massive poverty and high crime, presence of majority

formal housing stock but also possessing an informal housing component and have decaying formal engineering infrastructure that requires rehabilitation or upgrading. Besides these, they present a need for substantial improvements in maintenance and operating, low internal economic opportunities, low education and skill levels among the resident population and poor interconnectivity with its surrounding neighborhoods (Anke, 2009).

The Alexander Renewal Project (ARP) in this case has led to the upgrading of existing decaying housing environments and the subsequent creation of additional affordable housing opportunities, reduction of the high levels of unemployment, creation of clean, safe and healthy environment and has contributed to the reduction of the high levels of crime and violence.

In spite of all these, South African UR programs are militated by the legacy of apartheid, legislation and settlement planning, private sector investment decisions, political, social and economic transition and inter-governmental relationships, government capacity and financial constraints (Engelbrecht, 2004)

2.5.4.3 Kenyan Experience

In Kenya, urban renewal is a rather recent phenomenon (Karanja, 2014), hence the existence of scarce documentation of the same. It is thus necessary to look at the experience of other countries in history so as to evaluate and understand the process.

Although urban renewal exercises occur in all urban areas, efforts of renewal in Kenya are best demonstrated in the city of Nairobi which is the country's capital (Karanja, 2014).

Nairobi was first established as a transportation centre, which later grew to become an administrative centre. The site was set in June, 1899 (when the rail line reached Nairobi) because it offered a suitable stopping place between Mombasa and Kisumu. The place was well fed with Mbagathi and Mathare Rivers (Blevin and Bouczo, 1997); it had ample level land for railway tracts, sidings, quarters (Boedecker, 1936); an elevated cooler ground to the west suitable for residential purposes (Foran, 1950); an apparently deserted land offering freedom for land appropriation (Obudho and Owuor, 1991.); and the area was free from tropical diseases (Walmsley, 1957).

Once the railway depot was established in Nairobi, certain spatial patterns began to emerge – the railway station, a shopping centre, housing quarters and the Indian bazaar (Obudho and Owuor, 1991.). This layout basically followed the 1898 Plan for a Railway Town and the 1899 Plan for Railway Staff Quarters (Nevanlinna, 1996). The city was first incorporated in 1900 as the township of Nairobi. This marked the birth of local government in the (Tiwari, 1981). Nairobi was going to be a railway town for Europeans with a mixed European and Asian trading posts. It laid the foundation of the physical appearance of Nairobi as it is today, directly expressing the notions of segregation of the towns functions as well as segregation by class and race (Emig, S. and Ismail, Z., 1980)

In 1902, however, the Indian bazaar was razed down as a solution to the plague that infested the area and rebuilt (Otiso, 2005). This can be seen as the first major renewal activity in the history of Nairobi (Karanja, 2014).

The city had already become a large and flourishing area with settlements consisting mainly of the KUR buildings, separate residential areas for Europeans and Indians, and a small African settlement in Eastlands (Obudho and Owuor, 1991.). In 1905, Nairobi was confirmed as the capital of the country (Nairobi Urban Study Group, 1973) with seven distinct zones. These were the railway centre, the Indian bazaar, the European business and administrative centre, the railway quarters, the dhobi or washerman's quarters, the European residential suburbs, with the military barracks in the periphery of the town (Tiwari, 1981).

Since during this time growth of the town was controlled by economic forces, there was no definite pattern of coordination of development other than by the layout of a gridiron street pattern in the CBD (Samuel and Teresa, 2003). In an attempt to order the situation, a town-planning consultant was appointed in 1926 to make recommendations on zoning arrangements (Nairobi Urban Study Group, 1973). However, little was done to curb land speculation, and development occurred in an uncontrolled manner.

The resultative plan of 1928 used the concept of functionalism, to create a modern national city to cater for industrial expansion and the growing numbers of African wage-earners working in the industries (Samuel and Teresa, 2003). The plan also used the garden city concept to divide residential areas into neighborhood units. This zoning of the city was of the Plan for a Settler

Capital. It enhanced segregation, enclaves and spatial limits to the interest and advantage of the European settlers (Samuel and Teresa, 2003). The plan proposed massive traffic system restructuring, swamp and drainage clearance, density and building regulation and the attempt to make the city a monumental administrative center (Klos, 2008).

The colonial plan after the settler plan was done in 1948. This plan propagated further class segregation by the creation of distinct low and high income neighborhoods (Klos, 2008). According to White 1948, this plan for colonial capital marginalized the Africans who by this time the majority hence spreading informal urbanization (White, 1948). The plan mapped out the City Centre 1.8km x 0.45km (Kenya Centre) which was surrounded by government buildings and an axial sort of planning with the Law Courts. It also provided a new road network system (Musangi, 2003).

Up to 1950s, it is noteworthy that Nairobi was not free from rapid urbanization problems, which have persisted to date. Some of the earliest urbanization problems in Nairobi include transportation (Hake, 1977), housing Blevin and Bouczo (1997); Obudho (1987); drainage and sanitation (Tiwari, 1981), water and sewerage (Nairobi City Council 1974), overcrowding, poor sanitation and unhealthy living conditions (Achola, 2002).

By 1960s, Kenya was getting independent, its population had by far increased and the physical infrastructure needed to be stretched (Musangi, 2003). In response this, the Metropolitan Growth Strategy of 1973 was initiated through a collaboration with the United Nations. This strategy provided for; decentralization and development of alternative service centers; modifying, upgrading and extension of the road network; formulation of realistic housing programs (Klos, 2008); and extension of the city boundary to the west and northeast as and when required, as well as encouraging the growth of satellite towns surrounding the city, i.e. Thika, Athi River and Machakos (Nairobi Urban Study Group, 1973); (Samuel and Teresa, 2003). These centers were in such a way that they had their own industrial, residential, shopping and administrative (Klos, 2008); (Musangi, 2003). The centers were connected with the city centre through a road network system that included construction of major bypasses.

Another effort of the post-independence state was the 1984-1988 Nairobi City Commission Development Plan, that outlined development needs of all sectors: health and environment,

housing, social services, sewerage, manpower development, transport and public works and financial management (Nairobi City Commission , 1985). Again, nothing much was achieved as regards its implementation (Samuel and Teresa, 2003). During this era massive housing constructions and investment on infrastructure too were done, the city however started declining due to population pressure in the 1980s and 1990s. The decline was characterized by lack of public amenities such as toilets, insecurity, slummed areas and trashed streets (Karanja, 2014).

Today, renewal programs in Nairobi City are largely noticeable in the residential parts of the inner city and in the central business district itself. They range from Redevelopment projects, for example the Cooperative house that had been brought down during the August 7 1997 Bomblast; Housing improvements such as the vast slum upgrading programs of the Nairobi slums, NHC Lang'ata Housing Scheme; Streetscape improvements encompassing the Nairobi beautification programme; Transportation enhancement for instance The 50 km long Thika Super Highway Project which was funded by the African Development Bank, and links Nairobi City with Thika County; and Historic preservation projects of parks and open spaces such as Uhuru Park and Central Park.

Even so, UR programs are widely seen and heard of in the slum upgrading projects around the city. This is because the most pressing challenge in Nairobi is to improve the environmental conditions of the urban poor. Programs largely entail cleaning up the environment or making the environment safe for the dwellers of the area.

However, the success of these projects towards ridding slums and benefitting is questionable (Karanja, 2014). For example, in 2012, a newspaper article depicted a survey that was carried out in Soweto 2012 showing that only 15% of the respondents in the new housing units were initially slum dwellers (Tairo, 2012). These projects largely entail cleaning up the environment or making the environment safe for the dwellers of the area. However, the success of these projects towards ridding slums and benefitting is questionable (Karanja, 2014). For example, in 2012, a newspaper article depicted a survey that was carried out in Soweto 2012 showing that only 15% of the respondents in the new housing units were initially slum dwellers (Tairo, 2012). Apparently, the rest had rented out the houses and their leasers had gone back to the Slum. This resulted to the creation of more slums. The survey also found out that the residents preferred

improved road networks, improved sanitation, better incomes and proper drainage systems (Karanja, 2014).

The article further argued low cost housing as a viable solution engaged in a bid to reduce or remove slummed areas (Tairo, 2012). In view of this, The National Housing Corporation has made efforts to renew these slums without disrupting the residents by using the unused lands to develop new housing units.

The Nairobi County government has adopted renewal efforts and plans to renew ageing houses mostly in the Eastlands areas through public private partnership programs. Consultants have been selected and mandated to establish an Urban Renewal Plan described as ‘detailed and integrated short-term plans intended to guide development of towns and their immediate environs’ (Karanja, 2014). These consultants have also been tasked to take stock of the existing social and physical infrastructure and their conditions and eventually draw recommendations for the necessary measures to better the situation. Currently, Mombasa city is on board, currently undertaking redevelopment of its old cities (See appendix 6).

2.5.5 Nexus between Urban Renewal and Environmental Management

Agenda 21, (1992) emphasizes on environmental sustainability advocating for the protection of natural resources and systems including all biological diversities. It goes further to advocate for the use of energy efficient technologies and use of renewable energies. Projects oriented to renewal should aim at protecting the environment by reduction of pollution of any form, sustainable utilization and preservation of natural resources and ‘increasing awareness on ecological issues’. According to Mutlu (2009), qualities such as air quality, congestion, noise and principles of water harvesting, waste recycling and sustainable design should also be examined and effective measures implemented for proper environmental management.

A review of several literatures on UR reveals that heritage preservation should be part of urban renewal and must never be overlooked. This process should entail preserving heritage buildings, parks and structures of historical, cultural or architectural interest e.g. monuments, retaining the local colour of the community and the historical characteristics of different districts. According to Holcomb and Beauregard (1981), the historical characteristics refer to the old pattern of a city that gives the city its unique character and are necessary to maintain the city's vitality. The

present, past, and future history are all equally important in the making of a modern city. Urban renewal began in the late 19th century in developed nations and experienced an intense phase in the late 1940s (Ryn and Calthorpe, 1986).

In essence, UR should be implemented to effect sustainable development. It should rather result to the development of a better, clean and safe environment for biolife.

CHAPTER THREE
3. SOCIO-ECONOMIC, HOUSING AND BASIC URBAN
ENVIRONMENTAL CHARACTERISTICS

3.1 General Information

In this survey, there were a total of 384 respondents. Majority of the respondents were from Makongeni 29.9% (115 respondents) followed closely with those from Mbotela 29.4% (113 respondents). The residents from Soweto East and Kianda were 20.6% (79 respondents) and 20.1% (77 respondents respectively). These findings are shown in Table 3.1 below.

Table 3.1 Number and Percentage of respondents in the Sampled sites

Area	Respondents	Percent (%)
Kianda	77	20.1
Makongeni	115	29.9
Mbotela	113	29.4
Soweto East	79	20.6
Total	384	100.0

Source; Field Survey, 2016

Of importance to note is that majority of the Kianda and Soweto East residents had relocated from the larger Kibera slum while Residents in Makongeni and Mbotela came from Mukuru Slums. Much more specifically, those from Makongeni previously lived in Mukuru Kwa Njenga and Mukuru Kwa Reuben Slums while residents of Mbotela lived in Mukuru Sinai slum (See scope of project in Appendix 4 - Figures A, B1, B2 and B3).

3.2 Socio-Economic Characteristics

Of the 384 respondents, 57 % were female while 42 % were male (see figure 3.1). Majority were people of ages between 20 and 35. This Categorically, 9.9 % of the sample population were above 45 years, 10.7 % were between 41 and 45, 10.9 % were between 36 and 40 years,17.2 % were between 31 and 35, 26.6 % were between 26 and 30, 16.9 % were between 20 and 25 while those that were of age less than 20 were only 5.2 % (see Figure 3.2). As such we see that the

project largely encompassed people in the middle age bracket, majority being less than 40 years of age.

Figure 3.1 Gender Percentage (%)

Source; Field Survey, 2016

Figure 3.2 Age of Respondents

Source; Field Survey, 2016

Majority of the respondents in this survey were married people. From Figure 3.3 we can see that these formed 76.3 %, the singles were 19.0 %, the widowed 2.1% and the separated were 1.3%.

Figure 3.3 Marital Status of the Respondents

Source; Field Survey, 2016

Cumulatively, majority have received schooling up to secondary as from the results. From Figure 3.4, we see that 28.9% have attended school up to Primary Level, 49.2 % have attended up to Secondary level, 7.8 % have gone to Certificate level, some 8.1% have attended up to diploma level, and a 2.3% have a first degree.

Figure 3.4 Respondents' Level of Education

Source; Field Survey, 2016

Table 3.2 Respondents' Level of Education in the different sites

S/No.	Level of Education	Kianda		Makongeni		Mbotela		Soweto East		Total	
		#	%	#	%	#	%	#	%	#	%
1	Primary	24	31.2%	37	32.2%	27	23.9%	23	29.1%	111	28.9%
2	Secondary	35	45.5%	56	48.7%	55	48.7%	43	54.4%	189	49.2%
3	Certificate	3	3.9%	9	7.8%	14	12.4%	4	5.1%	30	7.8%
4	Diploma	7	9.1%	7	6.1%	11	9.7%	6	7.6%	31	8.1%
5	First Degree	4	5.2%	1	.9%	3	2.7%	1	1.3%	9	2.3%
6	PhD	1	1.3%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	1	.3%
7	Non-formal Education	1	1.3%	3	2.6%	2	1.8%	1	1.3%	7	1.8%
8	No response	2	2.6%	2	1.7%	1	.9%	1	1.3%	6	1.6%
	Total	77	100.0%	115	100.0%	113	100.0%	79	100.0%	384	100.0%

Source; Field Survey, 2016

As from Figure 3.5, Majority were of Christian faith, 99% whereas Islam faith formed the minority 1%.

Figure 3.5 Religion Indices

Source; Field Survey, 2016

From Figure 3.6, out of the 384 respondents, 26.8% were traders, 24.7% were unemployed, and 21.1% were in the private sector.

Figure 3.6 Occupation of Residents

Source; Field Survey, 2016

Although there is a large proportion of the unemployed, there is also a large number that have a source of income. As shown in Table 3.3, 9.1 % formed students, 8.3% were craftsmen doing

handwork, while retirees formed 1.1%. Specific information about the occupation instances for respondents in the different sites are displayed.

Table 3.3 Respondents Occupation Instances for in the Different Sites

S/No.	Occupation	Kianda		Makongeni		Mbotela		Soweto East		Total	
		#	%	#	%	#	%	#	%	#	%
1	Student	13	16.9%	4	3.5%	9	8.0%	9	11.4%	35	9.1%
2	Farming	4	5.2%	2	1.7%	2	1.8%	3	3.8%	11	2.9%
3	Craftsman	5	6.5%	17	14.8%	5	4.4%	5	6.3%	32	8.3%
4	Trading	16	20.8%	39	33.9%	29	25.7%	19	24.1%	103	26.8%
5	Retiree	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	3	2.7%	1	1.3%	4	1.0%
6	Private Sector Employment	20	26.0%	18	15.7%	24	21.2%	19	24.1%	81	21.1%
7	Public Sector Employment	6	7.8%	4	3.5%	5	4.4%	3	3.8%	18	4.7%
8	Unemployed	13	16.9%	29	25.2%	35	31.0%	18	22.8%	95	24.7%
9	No response	0	0.0%	2	1.7%	1	.9%	2	2.5%	5	1.3%
Total		77	100.0%	115	100.0%	113	100.0%	79	100.0%	384	100.0%

Source; Field Survey, 2016

From Figure 3.7, it is evident that majority of the respondents earn less than Ksh. 20,000 per month as income.

Figure 3.7 Average Monthly Income

Source; Field Survey, 2016

3.3 Housing Characteristics

There are approximately 2.5 million slum dwellers in about 200 settlements in Nairobi representing 60% of the Nairobi population that occupy just 6% of the land (Kibera Facts and Info, 2016). In Nairobi, slums are located near the Central Business District, near Industrial Area and on the periphery of the high income earning residents zones. In the slums, usually the rents are low hence preferred by majority who come to seek for employment. Poverty is sharply widespread in these slum areas. Houses are poorly structured using frail and wobbly building materials which are easily carried away during the heavy rains seasons (see Plate 3.1).

Plate 3.1 Frail Structures in Mukuru Kwa Njenga slum.

Source; Field Survey, 2016

According to (Gulis, Mulumba, Juma, and Kakosova, 2004), generally there is a poor spacing characteristic (house of 34 m) with remarkably insufficient ventilation (see Plate 3.2).

Plate 3.2 Poor Spacing of Structures in Soweto East

Source; Field Survey, 2016

The roofs of houses are made of iron sheets, tins while the walls are made of either mud, wood or iron sheets with few cemented floors (see Plate 3.3).

Poor structures and poor drainage systems see flowing waters especially during the rainy seasons passing through the houses posing a very serious challenge to the inhabitants who struggle to survive (Amendah, Buigut, and Mohamed, 2014). Again the single rooms and the bed sitters serve as the kitchen, sleeping area, dining room and many times as bathroom posing a great danger to health. With every space being utilized in these slum areas, it has been keenly noted that recently, flats have emerged (Gulis, Mulumba, Juma, and Kakosova, 2004).

Plate 3.3 Tin and paper roofs in Mukuru Kwa Njenga Slum

Source; Field Survey, 2016

In this survey 68% of the respondents reported to have been living in single rooms previously, while another category at 10.2% and 10.8% responded to have been living in bedsitters and one bedroomed house respectively (see Table 3.4).

A smaller minority lived in bigger houses. Majority of the residents in slums opt for houses where they shall incur the least rental charges, because they either run small businesses or have come to search for job employment in the city or are employed as day labourers in the industries in Nairobi. From the FGDs, most of them that used to live in bigger houses were structure owners, hence incurring for rent purposes (see Appendix 2).

Table 3.4 Type of Previous House for Respondents in Specific Segments

S/No.	Type of Previous House	Kianda		Makongeni		Mbotela		Soweto East		Total	
		#	%	#	%	#	%	#	%	#	%
1	Single Room	48	62.3%	71	61.7%	77	68.1%	65	82.3%	261	68.0%
2	Bedsitter	12	15.6%	13	11.3%	9	8.0%	5	6.3%	39	10.2%
3	One Bedroom	13	16.9%	20	17.4%	10	8.8%	6	7.6%	49	12.8%
4	Two Bedroom	2	2.6%	5	4.3%	10	8.8%	3	3.8%	20	5.2%
5	Three Bedroom	2	2.6%	5	4.3%	2	1.8%	0	0.0%	9	2.3%
6	No response	0	0.0%	1	.9%	5	4.4%	0	0.0%	6	1.6%
Total		77	100.0	115	100.0	113	100.0	79	100.0	384	100.0

Source; Field Survey, 2016

From Figure 3.8, majority of the respondents used to stay between 3 and 10 under the same roof. From the same figure, 49.5% of the respondents reported that they used to live between 3 and 5 people, while another 37.8% reported to have been living between 6-10 people in the same house.

From this, we can visualize the overcrowding issue in Mukuru and Kibera which is mainly due to poverty. Overcrowding is a major issue in the slum areas since it easily increases chance for disease spread, as it is in the case of Nairobi slums (Gulis, Mulumba, Juma, and Kakosova, 2004) and also increases chance for violence in homes.

A minority 8.3% used to live only 1 to 2 persons. Majority of these minority group were either students or had been given the houses by their kinsmen. On the other hand, from the discussions, part of this group were family heads who had come to the city to fend for their families back in the villages.

Figure 3.8 Number of Occupants in the Previous House

Source; Field Survey, 2016

Due to the nature of the RAP houses (see Figure 1.3), upon relocation, some families were forced to reorganize themselves so as to live comfortably in these houses. From the FGDs, the younger families and them that were initially few occupants benefited much more than them that were many in the same household. Large families that lived in one /two/ three bedroomed houses had to find other options for shelter in other parts of the slum away from the railway reserve or elsewhere.

According to Mwangi (1997), the lack of an explicit rental housing policy is prevalent in Kenya. Notably, rental housing issues have been inundated in the overall national housing policy first formulated in 1966 in Sessional Paper No.5, which rests as the only basis for national housing policy in Kenya (Ministry of Public Works, 1996). As such, different authorities design their own programs for the supply of rental housing in the country even in the slum set up where structure owners own the structures. Notably, the lack of specific consideration for rental housing in the national housing policy has been reinforced by more than three decades of centralized development models (Mwangi, 1997).

In this survey, it was clear that the Government owned all the slum land as such there would not be land owners. Structure owners put up structures so that tenants would live inside and thus benefit from rent. About 17% of the respondents were structure owners, hence did not pay rent, 75% rented structures to live inside while another 5% lived freely (see Figure 3.9). These that lived freely and were not structure owners were majorly dependants of structure owners.

Figure 3.9 Nature of occupancy

Source; Field Survey, 2016

As stated earlier due to the lack of a clear rental policy, it would be thus expected that there would be varied ranges of the rent bracket. Whereas a majority group of 34.1% were not comfortable to disclose the rent they used to pay, a 35.7% used to pay between KES 1001 and KES 2500, 18.5 % used to pay between KES 2,501 and KES 5,000 (see Figure 3.10).

Currently, there is a flat rate of only KES 800, which all PAPs / residents of the RAP Project pay yearly. From this we see that the rates have reduced drastically, which is a plus for the RAP project.

Figure 3.10 Monthly Rent Paid By Respondents in Their Previous Residence

Source; Field Survey, 2016

A group of 32.6 % reported that the buildings they used to live in previously were between 10 and 19 years of age, 25.5% reported that theirs were below 10 years, 3.6% had their buildings 30 years and above and 2.3% reported that theirs were between 20 and 29 years (see Figure 3.11). From this it is evident that there is a growth of slums generally. Again, from the discussions, structures need to be replaced from time, due to the precarious nature of the structures/ due to common instances such as fire outbreaks.

Figure 3.11 Age of Building in Years

Source; Field Survey, 2016

From Figure 3.12, the walls of structures that they used to live in were mainly made of iron sheets (58%). Majority of structure owners use these because they are generally cheaper and can be easily undone and the structure shifted to another place in cases of worst case scenarios of eviction, floods etc. Then 25% of the respondents reported to have been living in stone walled houses, another 12% in mud walled houses and another 5% in timber walled houses.

Figure 3.12 Material Used for Wall Construction of the Respondent's Houses

Source; Field Survey, 2016

The roofing materials used were either iron sheets or aluminium sheets, mainly in poor conditions, having been re-used from time to time.

In general, 29.4% responded that their buildings were physically sound, 31% reported that the buildings that they lived in needed minor repairs, buildings for 21.4 % of the respondents needed major repairs, while the other 12.5% reported that their houses were completely dilapidated (see Table 3.5). From this, it is evident that the majority of the buildings needed repairs either minor or major or total redevelopment. This could have been attributed to the poor materials used for construction as well as other factors such as poor siting, drainage problems and other factors as we shall see in the next sections.

Table 3.5 Respondents View on the Structural Condition of the Building They Used To Live In Before

S/No.	Structural Condition of Buildings	Kianda		Makongeni		Mbotela		Soweto East		Total	
		#	%	#	%	#	%	#	%	#	%
1	Physically sound	30	39.0%	34	29.6%	35	31.0%	14	17.7%	113	29.4%
2	Needing minor repairs	20	26.0%	40	34.8%	32	28.3%	27	34.2%	119	31.0%
3	Needing major repairs	13	16.9%	19	16.5%	29	25.7%	21	26.6%	82	21.4%
4	Dilapidated	9	11.7%	16	13.9%	9	8.0%	14	17.7%	48	12.5%
5	No response	5	6.5%	6	5.2%	8	7.1%	3	3.8%	22	5.7%
Total		77	100.0%	115	100.0%	113	100.0%	79	100.0%	384	100.0%

Source; Field Survey, 2016

Majority of the respondents do not prefer life in the slums. This is due to the common intricacies which lack in the slums. These include high crime rates, lack of basic sanitation facilities and basic services, overcrowding of areas, lack of security among other factors.

Of the total respondents, (37%) reported that the previous state was generally not good, 35.7% reported that it was fair, a 16% reported that the area was good, and a 4.7% reported that the old state was very good (see Figure 3.13). Most relatively prefer the new area seemingly because of the facilities therein and the structure of the houses themselves besides several amenities that the RAP units constitute of.

Figure 3.13 Views Concerning the Previous State

Source; Field Survey, 2016

3.4 Basic Urban Environmental Characteristics

3.4.1 Water

During the rainy season, water costs are reduced because residents tap water from their roofs. Otherwise, the price of water is expensive, described to be almost four times the cost at which the council sells to the vendors (Lee-Smith and Lamba, 1998).

Plate 3.4 People Queueing to Buy Water

Source; (Kibera Facts and Info, 2016)

Plate 3.5 Water Meter Kiosk In Kibera.

Source; (Kibera Facts and Info, 2016)

3.4.1.1. Source of water for drinking, cooking and washing

In their previous areas, most respondents (50%) used to obtain water from the local water vendors (see Table 3.6). From the focus group discussion, these water vendors initially used to provide water from the city council but switched on to water meter kiosks when The World Bank Group introduced water chambers in the slum.

A group of 42.4% used to obtain water from the City Council where some would pay together with the rent while others would pay it as a separate bill depending on the amount of water used. Some would use the water directly while others could apply measures to make the water safe for human consumption.

Table 3.6 Previous Source of Drinking Water for the Respondents

	Source	Frequency	Percent (%)
Valid	County Council	163	42.4
	Borehole	5	1.3
	Communal Well	2	.5
	River/Stream	1	.3
	Bottled Water	2	.5
	Local Water Vendors	192	50.0
	No response	No response	19
Total		384	100.0

Source; Field Survey, 2016

Currently, 70.2% of the residents obtain water from the city council (see Table 3.7). This has been due to the fact that the RAP Project installed a water tap and meter for every house. There is also a monthly flat rate of KES 200 for water, which exceeds upon exceeding the specified units catered for by the flat rate. Every house also, apart from the meter, is entitled to a water tank (100 Litres) on the roof tops for water storage. Others, 27.4 %, also obtain water from the local water vendors. This is as a result of water rationing instances.

Table 3.7 Current Source of Drinking Water for the Respondents

S/No.	Source of Drinking Water	Responses	
		N	Percent
1	County Council	294	70.2%
2	Borehole	13	1.8%
3	Communal well	1	.1%
4	Bottled water	3	.4%
5	Local water vendors	193	27.4%

Source; Field Survey, 2016

Conclusively, it is evident that there is a significant difference between the previous and the current sources of water for the residents, $\chi^2 (30, N=384) = 176.795, p=0.000$ (see Table 3.8).

Table 3.8 showing Chi-square Tests result on previous and current water sources

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	176.795 ^a	30	0.000
Likelihood Ratio	111.166	30	0.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	141.685	1	0.000
N of Valid Cases	384		

Source; Field Survey, 2016

3.4.1.2. Frequency of flow of piped water

Of them that had their water supply from the county council in the slum, an overall 34.4% reported that they used to get water daily. This water had been installed in the compound of the people, having organised themselves in clusters. About 12.2% reported to have been getting water only once per week, 15.5% reported to have been getting twice per week, and a 6.8% reported to have not been getting water at all. It is clear that in the previous residences, the larger majority that used to obtain water from the city council had it daily (see Table 3.9).i.e. in Kianda, 40.3%, Makongeni, 34.8%, 29.2% in Mbotela and 35.4% in Soweto East.

Table 3.9 Frequency of Piped Water Flow in the Previous Residence

S/N	Frequency of flow of Piped Water	Kianda		Makongeni		Mbotela		Soweto East		Total Percent
		#	%	#	%	#	%	#	%	%
1	Daily	31	40.3%	40	34.8%	33	29.2%	28	35.4%	34.4%
2	Once per week	6	7.8%	9	7.8%	15	13.3%	17	21.5%	12.2%
3	Twice per week	10	13.0%	6	5.2%	29	25.7%	13	16.5%	15.1%
4	Not at all	8	10.4%	2	1.7%	9	8.0%	7	8.9%	6.8%
5	No response	22	28.6%	58	50.4%	27	23.9%	14	17.9%	31.5%
Total		77	100.0%	115	100.0%	113	100.0%	79	100.0%	100.0%

Source; Field Survey, 2016

Currently, 12.5 % receive water daily. 25.3 % receive water once per week, 23.7% receive water twice per week while 2.9 % do not obtain water from the city council at all. Soweto East PAPs had the greatest challenge of water and as such water is available only once in a week (see majority bracket 79.7% on Table 3.10).

Table 3.10 Frequency of Piped Water Flow In The Current Area

S/No	Frequency of Flow of Piped Water	Kianda		Makongeni		Mbotela		Soweto East		Total
		#	%	#	%	#	%	#	%	%
1	Daily	17	22.1%	11	9.6%	14	12.4%	6	7.6%	12.5%
2	Once per week	8	10.4%	11	9.6%	15	13.3%	63	79.7%	25.3%
3	Twice per week	25	32.5%	12	10.4%	47	41.6%	7	8.9%	23.7%
4	Not at all	6	7.8%	4	3.5%	1	.9%	0	0.0%	2.9%
5	No response	21	27.3%	77	66.9%	36	31.9%	3	3.8%	35.6%
Total		77	100.0%	115	100.0%	113	100.0%	79	100.0%	100.0%

Source; Field Survey, 2016

Statistically, there is no significant difference between the regularity of piped water flow in the previous and the current areas $t(383) = 0.516, p=0.606$. See Table 3.11.

Table 3.11 Paired T Test on Frequency of Flow of Piped Water

	Paired Differences				t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower				Upper
Regularity of flow of piped water: Before vs Current	1.117	42.417	2.165	-3.139	5.373	0.516	383	0.606

Source; Field Survey, 2016

Generally in both situations, there seems to be a persistent challenge of water availability. From Focus Group Discussions with Makongeni PAPs for instance, water has technical issues, so a relatively small percentage of the respondents access the water from the city council. The rest buy water from the local water vendors.

Generally from the researchers' observation, the PAPs have developed some coping mechanisms to these water availability issues. Others have bought water tanks and basins to store water, because the 100 litre water tanks availed to them are not enough for them, considering the high rationing instances. Sometimes the water is under low pressure and can't get to the water tanks.

3.4.1.3 Water Payment

While some respondents were not comfortable to share the much they used to pay for piped water in the area, 44.8% of the reported to have been paying for the piped water while another 23.2% reported not to have been paying at all. Of this 44.8%, 1.8% used to pay less than KES 100, 20.6% paid between KES 101 and KES 500 whereas 8.6% paid between KES 501 and KES 1000. Minority groups of 0.8%, 0.5% and 0.5% used to pay between KES 1001-1500, KES 1501-2000 and KES 2000 respectively (see Table 3.12).

From Table 3.12, comparing Kianda and Soweto East, which are in Kibera Slum, most respondents used to pay between KES 101 and KES 1000 i.e. 23.4% and 20.3% payed between KES 101 and KES 500 in Kianda and Soweto East respectively. Another majority 10.4% and 10.1% in Kianda and Soweto East respectively reported to have been paying between KES 501 and KES 1000.

As stated earlier in this dissertation, Majority of Makongeni and Mbotela PAPs lived in Mukuru slum. To be much more specific, Makongeni PAPs lived in Mukuru Kwa Njenga and Mukuru Kwa Reuben before while Mbotela hosts PAPs that lived in Mukuru Kwa Sinai. These too almost had similar circumstances. About 6.1% and 33.6% of respondents from Makongeni and Mbotela respectively reported to have been paying between KES 101 and KES 500 while another 3.5% and 8.0% reported to have been paying between KES 501 and KES 1000.

Table 3.12 Monthly Water Payment in the Previous Residence

S/No	Water Bill per Month	Kianda		Makongeni		Mbotela		Soweto East		Total
		#	%	#	%	#	%	#	%	%
1	Below KES 100	1	1.3%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	2	2.5%	0.8%
2	Between KES 101-500	18	23.4%	7	6.1%	38	33.6%	16	20.3%	20.6%
3	Between 501-1000	8	10.4%	4	3.5%	9	8.0%	8	10.1%	7.6%
4	Between KES 1001-1500	1	1.3%	1	0.9%	1	0.9%	0	0.0%	0.8%
5	Between KES 1501-2000	0	0.0%	1	0.9%	0	0.0%	1	1.3%	0.5%
6	Above 2000	2	2.6%	0	0.0%	1	.9%	0	0.0%	0.8%
7	No response	47	61.0%	102	88.7%	64	56.6%	52	65.8%	69.0%
Total		77	100.0	115	100.0	113	100.0	79	100.0	100.0

Source; Field Survey, 2016

Currently, 45.8% reported that they pay for water while 24% reported that they did not yet start paying for water although it is being billed that they would be given their bills once they would be processed. Comparing the response rates across the different segments (see Table 3.13), it's evident that majority of residents pay for water between KES 101 and KES 1000. Another majority of 26.2% paid between KES 501 and KES 1000.

Table 3.13 Monthly Water Payment in the Current Residence

S/No	Water Bill per Month	Kianda		Makongeni		Mbotela		Soweto East		Total
		#	%	#	%	#	%	#	%	%
1	Below KES 100	2	8.3%	1	3.8%	4	8.7%	0	0.0%	5.6%
2	Between KES 101-500	10	41.7%	20	76.9%	35	76.1%	14	46.7%	62.7%
3	Between 501-1000	8	33.3%	5	19.2%	6	13.0%	14	46.7%	26.2%
4	Between KES 1001-1500	2	8.3%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	1	3.3%	2.4%
5	Between KES 1501-2000	1	4.2%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	1	3.3%	1.6%
6	Above 2000	1	4.2%	0	0.0%	1	2.2%	0	0.0%	1.6%
Total		24	100.0%	26	100.0%	46	100.0%	30	100.0%	100.0%

Source; Field Survey, 2016

Conclusively, there is no significant difference between the two scenarios, in terms of water payment $t(383) = -0.171, p=0.864$ (See Table 3.14).

Table 3.14 Paired T Test on Water Payment

	Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower	Upper			
Payment for piped water : Before vs Current	-0.565	64.690	3.301	-7.056	5.926	-0.171	383	0.864

Source; Field Survey, 2016

3.4.1.4 Distance to water source

Previously, 50.3% of the respondents used to obtain water within a distance between 0 and 50 metres while 22.1% obtained water within a distance of between 51 and 100 metres. 6.0% obtained water at a distance which was between 101 metres and 200 metres, 6.3% obtained at a distance between 201 and 500 metres and 6.3 % obtained water from a distance that was over 500 metres see Figure 3.14.

Figure 3.14 Comparison between Previous and Current Distance to Water Source

Source; Field Survey, 2016

From Figure 3.14, it is evident that respondents used to stay near water sources as majority accessed water at distances of between 0 and 100 metres i.e. a gross of 72.4% (50.3% accessed water between 0 and 50 m and 22.1% that accessed water at a distance between 51 and 100 metres) accessed water at this distance.

Currently, 58.6% access water at a distance between 0 and 50 metres, 6.8% access at distance between 51 and 100 metres, 6.3% at distance between 101 and 200 metres, 4.7 % at distance between 201 and 500 metres while 13.5 % access at a distance over 500 metres.

Figure 3.15 Previous Distance to Water Source.

Source; Field Survey, 2016

There is a significant difference between the distance of water sources in both the previous and the current situation $t(384) = 0.467, p < 0.000$. See Table 3.15.

Table 3.15 Paired T-Test on Distance to Water Source

	Number	Correlation	Sig.
Distance of water source(in meters) to the house: Before vs Current	384	0.467	0.000

Source; Field Survey, 2016

In the current area, the location of a PAP's house would determine accessibility to different facilities among which water is one of them. The houses are long being served with two exits which also serve as the segment entrances except for the case of Makongeni that is exceptional because it lacks a fence / a partitioning structure. Despite the easy accessibility to Makongeni, the water point/location of water vendors stands at a single area and as such 37.4% as from Figure 3.16 access water at a distance that is over 500 metres.

Despite of this, there is a cumulative increment of PAPs near to water source between 0 and 50 metres. In the previous account, 79.4% of the respondents would access water at a distance less 200 metres, but in the current area, only 71.4% can access water at the same distance.

Figure 3.16 Current Distance to Water Source in the Different Segments

Source; Field Survey, 2016

There are varied views concerning water supply in the area. Cumulatively, 14 % of the respondents reported that water supply is very good, 31 % reported that it is good, according to 28 % it is fair while according to 22 % water supply is not good at all. (see Figure 3.17).

Figure 3.17 Views on Current Water Supply

Source; Field Survey, 2016

Again this depended greatly on the segment in case, because the four different segments have different experiences. In Kianda for instance, 24.7% finds water supply to be good while another 31.2% finds the situation fair. In this segment, not all houses are fixed to the water supply system yet and as such, there is a mix of water source. Others get water from boreholes and others buy from market forty-two.

In Makongeni, 4.3% view water supply as very good, 27% of the respondents view water supply to be fair while the large majority of 49.6% view the condition as not good at all. This report according to Makongeni is as such because of technical failures hence water does not get into every household. PAPs are therefore forced to buy water from vendors, selling KES 20 per jelician of fresh water and KES 5 per jelician of borehole water.

In Mbotela, majority 52.2% find the situation very good, 23.9% find the situation to be good, while another 5.3% finds the situation as fair. Water in this segment is sufficient, having been successfully fixed in every house. In Soweto East, 20.3% find water supply to be very good , another 45.6% view it as good while 20.3% view it to be fair (see Figure 3.18).

Figure 3.18 Views on Current Water Supply in the Different Segments

Source; Field Survey, 2016

3.4.2 Market

A major characteristic of the slum areas usually, is that there are mixed land uses which usually follow no plan or order. Retail shops are virtually everywhere; residents readily obtain their supplies depending on the commodity they want (See Plate 3.6 – 3.8).

Plate 3.6 Soweto East Residents' Structures Proximity to the Retail Shops.

Source; Field Survey, 2016

Again, residents prefer to go for their major supplies in the markets they used to go initially while living in the slums. This is very typical for them at Soweto East and Kianda who used to go to Laini Saba market. PAPA's at Makongeni and Mbotela currently go to Ouru Market and Muthurwa Market because these markets are nearer to their residence than their previous '*Soko ya Reli*' market.

Plate 3.7 Mukuru Kwa Njenga ‘Soko Ya Reli’ Market Area

Source; Field Survey, 2016

Plate 3.8 Mukuru Kwa Reuben ‘Soko Ya Reli’ Market Area

Source; Field Survey, 2016

3.4.2.1 Distance to nearest retail shop for daily supplies

Before renewal, 58.1% of the respondents could access their retail shops located at a proximity distance between 0 and 50 m. In the current residence only a 37.8% are able to access their retail shops at the same distance (see Figure 3.19).

Figure 3.19: Previous and Current Distance to the Market

Source; Field Survey, 2016

Before renewal, 20.6 % were able to access their nearest retail shops located at a distance between 51 to 100 metres but after renewal, 18.5 % are able to access the retail shops at the same distance. In like manner, about 8.6% and 10.7% are able to access nearest retail shops at a distance between 101 to 200 metres while 4.7% then and 14.3% now access at a distance between 201 to 500 metres in the previous and current areas respectively.

A majority 15.9% access the retail shops at over 500 metres. Clearly due to the structural design of the RAP units, these results must have been so. The RAP Units are long in length along the railway line, with one or two access points. As such, PAP specific house locations determine their proximity not only to the retail shops but also to the market (see Figure 3.20).

Figure 3.20 Previous vs Current Distances to Retail Market

Source; Field Survey, 2016

Table 3.16 Paired T- Tests on Distance to Nearest Retail Shop for Daily Supplies

	Paired Differences				t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower				Upper
Distance to the nearest retail shop: Before vs Current	-0.492	13.167	0.672	-1.813	0.829	-0.732	383	0.464

Source; Field Survey, 2016

From the Table 3.16, there is no significant difference between the previous and current distances covered in a bid to access their nearest retail shops i.e. $t(25) = 253.6$, $p=0.464$. Generally, most of the PAPs prefer to go to the market places that they used to go before relocation. Even so, others still had to cope with the new situation, opting to go to the nearby markets.

Just like before, some of the PAPs in Kianda go to ‘Forty-Two’ Market, while in Soweto East, some go to Laini Saba Market although there are other markets such as Toi Market where others go. A characteristic of Kibera’s major markets from the FGDs is that they are situated in specific areas or zones.

Even so, small scale commercial framework is really vast and highly dense in its nature, with a high ability of encroachability; to an extent of disrupting the transport systems within the area (see Plate 3.9). From a discussion with the Leaders and PAPs of Makongeni and Mbotela previously living in Mukuru (Kwa Njenga, Reuben and Sinai), Markets within the neighborhood consist of temporary shacks with goods laid out and packed up every day and are situated along the railway line, and pathways to trap the heavy pedestrian traffic using these areas on their way to Industrial Area in the morning and even (see Plate 3.10).

Plate 3.9 Heavy Traffic Using the Railway for Transit.

Source; Kibera Facts and Info, 2016

Plate 3.10 Mukuru Kwa Sinai Railway Line Encroached By Business Activity.

Source; Field Survey, 2016

3.4.2.2. Market Conditions

In describing the market conditions of their environment from Table 3.17, 45.3% agree that their previous markets were fairly clean and hygienic, 31.3% described their market as not clean and hygienic at all, and 17.7% described them as clean and hygienic, while a relatively small 3.4% described their markets to be very clean and hygienic.

Table 3.17 Previous Market Condition

S/No.	Market Environment	Kianda		Makongeni		Mbotela		Soweto East		Total	
		#	%	#	%	#	%	#	%	#	%
1	Very clean and hygienic	7	9.1%	2	1.7%	2	1.8%	2	2.5%	13	3.4%
2	Clean and hygienic	19	24.7%	20	17.4%	17	15.0%	12	15.2%	68	17.7%
3	Fairly clean and hygienic	34	44.2%	53	46.1%	47	41.6%	40	50.6%	174	45.3%
4	Not clean and hygienic at all	15	19.5%	38	33.0%	42	37.2%	25	31.6%	120	31.3%
5	No response	2	2.6%	2	1.7%	5	4.4%	0	0.0%	9	2.3%
Total		77	100.0%	115	100.0%	113	100.0%	79	100.0%	384	100.0%

Source; Field Survey, 2016

Approximately 51.8% reported that their current market environments are clean and hygienic, 27.6% reported that they are fairly clean and hygienic, 12.2% view them to be very clean and hygienic while only a minority 4.4% view them as not clean and hygienic at all (see Table 3.18). Contrasting view on market conditions per study area is as shown in Figure 3.21.

Table 3.18 General Views on the Market Environment

	Frequency	Percent (%)	Valid Percent (%)	Cumulative Percent (%)
Very clean and hygienic	47	12.2	12.2	12.2
Clean and hygienic	199	51.8	51.8	64.1
Fairly clean and hygienic	106	27.6	27.6	91.7
Not clean and hygienic at all	17	4.4	4.4	96.1
No response	15	3.9	3.9	100.0

Source; Field Survey, 2016

Figure 3.21 Current Market Environment

Source; Field Survey, 2016

From these results, there is a significant difference between the market condition in the previous and current situations χ^2 (16, N=384) =254.403, p=0.000 (see Table 3.19). The markets are cleaner, and well-ordered for example in 'Ouru' and 'Muthurwa' Markets unlike the 'Soko ya Reli' in Mukuru that had completely encroached into the rail road.

Table 3.19 Chi-Square Test on Market Condition

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	254.403 ^a	16	0.000
Likelihood Ratio	118.499	16	0.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	175.533	1	0.000
N of Valid Cases	384		

Source; Field Survey, 2016

3.4.3 Waste Management

While poor management of solid waste is a general problem in Kenya, it is probably worst in Nairobi (Hardoy, Mitlin, and Satterthwaite, 2003). Usually, there exist no garbage collection systems in the slums. As such, heaps of wastes lie commonly in the slum and have been identified by the same authors as one of the slum's most visible environmental problems.

In the previous area in the slum, the respondents majorly disposed their waste through open dumping (see Figure 3.22). As we shall see later in this dissertation, these have consequences of poor drainage and health issues which these people had to cope with. Where this was different, there were private collectors who would collect the waste twice per week or once per week or daily as seen from Figure 3.23.

Figure 3.22 Previous Method of Waste Collection

Source; Field Survey, 2016

Figure 3.23 Frequency of Waste Collection in the Previous Residence

Source; Field Survey, 2016

Table 3.20 Chi-Square Tests on Methods of Waste Collection

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	161.342 ^a	20	.000
Likelihood Ratio	63.194	20	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	97.228	1	.000
Number of Valid Cases	384		

Source; Field Survey, 2016

From Table 3.20, there is a significant difference between the methods of waste collection in the two accounts. $\chi^2 = (20, N=384) = 161.342, p= 0.000$. Currently, waste is majorly disposed by private collectors who are hired by the PAPs themselves who pay KES 500 towards garbage collection and security services within the RAP units. Whereas this is the case, others still, a 3.6%, still practice open dumping while another relatively small percentage 0.3% reported to carry out open burning (see Figure 3.24). About 75.8% reported that waste collection is carried out once in every week whereas 8.6% reported that it is carried out twice per week, and another 1.3% reported that it is carried out daily (see Figure 3.24).

Figure 3.24 Current Method of Waste Collection

Source; Field Survey, 2016

Figure 3.25 Current Frequency of Waste Collection

Source; Field Survey, 2016

From the focused group discussions, it was evident that in the previous homes, the National Youth Service (NYS) used to periodically clean the environment in some sections of Kibera and as such had contributed greatly towards the cleanliness and hygiene in those areas. Nonetheless,

majority reported that waste collection was not being done at all see Table 3.21 (37.7% in Kianda, 27.0% in Makongeni, 34.5% in Mbotela and 53.2% in Soweto East.)

Table 3.21 Frequency of Waste Collection in the Previous Slum Area

S/No	Frequency of Waste Collection	Kianda		Makongeni		Mbotela		Soweto East		Total	
		#	%	#	%	#	%	#	%	#	%
1	Daily	8	10.4%	4	3.5%	1	.9%	4	5.1%	17	4.4%
2	Once per week	26	33.8%	52	45.2%	52	46.0%	13	16.5%	143	37.2%
3	Twice per week	6	7.8%	13	11.3%	1	.9%	2	2.5%	22	5.7%
4	Not at all	29	37.7%	31	27.0%	39	34.5%	42	53.2%	141	36.7%
5	No response	8	10.4%	15	13.0%	20	17.7%	18	22.8%	61	15.9%
Total		77	100.0%	115	100.0%	113	100.0%	79	100.0%	384	100.0%

Source; Field Survey, 2016

Table 3.22 Paired T-Tests On Frequency Of Waste Collection

	Paired Differences				t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower				Upper
Frequency of waste collection: Before vs. After	5.641	36.543	1.865	1.974	9.307	3.025	383	0.003

Source; Field Survey, 2016

On the frequency of waste collection, there is a significant difference between the two accounts, $t(383) = 3.025, p < 0.05$.

Comparing Table 3.21 and Table 3.23, most respondents have their waste collection done once in a week, with minimal cases of where the wastes are completely not being collected. This happens when the PAP is not available during the period when the wastes are being collected. In Makongeni, one of the Saccos has put in place strategies to collect waste in their zone twice per week (See Table 3.23).

Table 3.23 Frequency of Waste Collection in the Current Area

S/No.	Frequency of Waste Collection	Kianda		Makongeni		Mbotela		Soweto East		Total	
		#	%	#	%	#	%	#	%	#	%
1	Daily	3	3.9%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	2	2.5%	5	1.3%
2	Once per week	64	83.1%	69	60.0%	103	91.2%	55	69.6%	291	75.8%
3	Twice per week	7	9.1%	18	15.7%	4	3.5%	4	5.1%	33	8.6%
4	Not at all	0	0.0%	6	5.2%	1	.9%	2	2.5%	9	2.3%
5	No response	3	3.9%	22	19.1%	5	4.4%	16	20.3%	46	12.0%
Total		77	100.0%	115	100.0%	113	100.0%	79	100.0%	384	100.0%

Source; Field Survey, 2016

When the respondents were asked their views concerning management of waste in the current area, Generally 18% viewed it to be very good, 44% described it to be good, and 24% viewed it to be fair while only 3% said that it was not good at all. Generally, the PAPs while in the slums, they never used to pay for waste collection but in this new area, they are forced to pay for some of these services that were free before.

Figure 3.26 Views on Waste Collection in the New Area

Source; Field Survey, 2016

Others too have had difficulty while adapting themselves with the new environment and culture of putting wastes into paper bags and then keeping them while awaiting disposal. In the previous slum area, the rail lands were areas for dumping the wastes but this is not again possible, because of the design of the RAP buildings that are built facing away the railway line (see Plate 3.11).

Plate 3.11 RAP Buildings Facing Away From the Railway Line.

Source: RAP Files, 2014

Figure 3.27 Views on Waste Collection in the Current Residence

Source; Field Survey, 2016

From the discussions, Majority as from Figure 3.26 and Figure 3.27 prefer current waste collection. Besides the environment of the RAP units being sight friendly, the PAPs are already appreciating an environment that is friendly for them to live and stay and for children to play. As from a later section in this dissertation, diseases have largely minimised due to environmental cleanliness efforts.

3.4.4 Drainage

3.4.4.1 Type of Toilet Facility

In this survey, 76% of the respondents reported to have been using communal toilets, whereas 16% reported to have had toilets meant for their households only (See Figure 3.28). Relatively, 56.5% had their toilets as pit latrines, 34.1% used public toilets, and 3.4% used bucket method while another 3.1% used closets (See Table 3.24).

Figure 3.28 Previous Mode of Toilet Usage

Source; Field Survey, 2016

Table 3.24 Type of Toilet Facility in the Previous Residence

S/No.	Type of Toilet Facility	Kianda		Makongeni		Mbotela		Soweto East		Total	
		#	%	#	%	#	%	#	%	#	%
1	Pit latrine	48	62.3%	76	66.1%	53	46.9%	40	50.6%	217	56.5%
2	Public	21	27.3%	30	26.1%	45	39.8%	35	44.3%	131	34.1%
3	Bucket method	1	1.3%	2	1.7%	6	5.3%	4	5.1%	13	3.4%
4	Closet	5	6.5%	4	3.5%	3	2.7%	0	0.0%	12	3.1%
5	No response	2	2.6%	3	2.6%	6	5.3%	0	0.0%	11	2.9%
Total		77	100.0%	115	100.0%	113	100.0%	79	100.0%	384	100.0%

Source; Field Survey, 2016

Generally Kibera slum is contaminated with human and animal faeces and all sorts of wastes which are worsened by open sewages and lack of drainage (Hardoy, Mitlin, and Satterthwaite, 2003). Discussions with PAPs at Soweto East verified this as they stated clearly that generally toilets were limited in the area before. In fact some had no toilets at all, yet they were living several households together in a cluster. While the toilet facilities were available, most complained that they would face the challenge of poor accessibility. Slum residents would pay at least KES5 / KES10 so as to use the public toilets owned by businessmen and individuals (see Plate 3.12).

At night due to insecurity reasons, some people especially the most vulnerable of the society like children would result to ‘flying toilets’ method as a result of having no other option. In this case they would excrete in paper bags and then would throw at night, landing elsewhere, being left unattended to decay. Where there were pit latrines, once they got full users would be forced to contribute for manual removal of the human waste for disposal.

Plate 3.12 Fresh Life Public Toilet in Mukuru Slum.

Source; Field Survey, 2016

From Table 3.25, there is a significant difference between the type of toilet facility in the previous and the current situation, $\chi^2 = (16, N = 384) = 168.229, p = 0.000$. In the current set up, all houses have been allocated with a flushing closet, furnished with water which although as described earlier in this report is not adequate.

Table 3.25 Chi-Square Test on the Type of Toilet Facility

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	168.229 ^a	16	0.000
Likelihood Ratio	65.903	16	0.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	149.444	1	0.000
N of Valid Cases	384		

Source; Field Survey, 2016

3.4.4.2 Type and Condition of Drainage

As identified by several authors, Nairobi's sewerage system is generally poor, and the waste and disposal system dysfunctional. But even this system is not available to residents of slum settlements as they have limited or no access to the public sewer lines and waste disposal systems. Rudimentary hand-constructed earthen channels acting as open sewers are common in the slum settlements, (see Plate 3.13), often coming into contact with drinking water pipes and many times passes right in front of houses (Amnesty International, 2009).

Plate 3.13 Lack of Sewer in the Slum.

(Source: Field survey)

This definitely is the case from this survey where 58.1 % responded that they had no drainage at all, whereas a 31.3% reported that they were connected to sewer lines which often broke down. From a field survey in Mukuru slum, a plot with several houses and several commercial units lacked toilets and also a proper drainage system. Relatively 7.3 % of the respondents reported that they were being served with a treatment plant (See Figure 3.29). All these efforts largely have come about through assistance from the International Communities, The Nairobi City County Government, Community Based Organizations e.g., Umande Trust, Pamoja Trust and Cooperatives.

Generally, 51.8 % viewed the drainage system as not good at all, 27.3% viewed that drainage to be fair, and another 11.5% viewed it to be good while 4.9% viewed it to be very good (see Figure 3.30). Them that had a good/ very good perception of the drainage systems from the discussions are majorly them that had their own private facilities for their household only.

Figure 3.29 Previous Type of Drainage System

Source; Field Survey, 2016

Figure 3.30 Views on the Condition of the Drainage System in the Previous Residence.

Source; Field Survey, 2016

There is a significant difference between the type of drainage system in the previous and current areas, $\chi^2 = (9, N = 384) = 132.440, p = 0.000$. (See Table 3.26).

Table 3.26 Chi-Square Test on the Type of Drainage System

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	132.440 ^a	9	0.000
Likelihood Ratio	50.460	9	0.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	117.395	1	0.000
N of Valid Cases	384		

Source; Field Survey, 2016

Figure 3.31 Current Type of Drainage System

Source; Field Survey, 2016

Figure 3.32 Views on Current Condition of the Drainage System

Source; Field Survey, 2016

In the RAP Units, all houses have been connected to a sewer line with really proper drainage. From Figure 3.32, most respondents view the current drainage system to be either good, or very good. Respective views per study area are as shown in the same table. The sewers are well dug serving all the units efficiently (see Plate 3.14). A storm sewer drain has also been provided to trap running water from the pavement and neighborhood and as such, there is no stagnation of water.

Plate 3.14 Sewer and Drainage connections in the RAP Units

Source; Rap Files, 2014

CHAPTER FOUR

4. HEALTH, ENERGY, SECURITY, ENVIRONMENTAL AWARENESS, AND FIRE ATTRIBUTES OF THE AREA.

This chapter focusses on other environmental sustainability attributes that the project covered. As stated above, these attributes include health and energy issues, security, preservation, environmental awareness of the residents and fire attributes. They were categorically analyzed with view of being short-term resultatives of the UR project at stake.

4.1 Health Issues

4.1.1 Cases and Type of Disease Outbreak

The survey set out to determine whether respondents had witnessed any disease outbreak in their previous residence. Of the 384 respondents, 42% acclaimed that they had not witnessed while 55% had witnessed several disease outbreaks (see Figure 4.1). A 16.4% reported that they had witnessed Malaria outbreak, while 10.9% had witnessed Typhoid outbreak. 29.4% had witnessed Cholera outbreak and 0.8% had witnessed Amoeba cases (see Table 4.1).

Figure 4.1 Per cent Respondents That Had Witnessed Disease Outbreaks in the Previous Residence.

Source; Field Survey, 2016

Table 4.1 Specific Disease Outbreak

Disease	Respondents	Percent (%)	Valid Percent (%)	Cumulative Percent (%)
Malaria	63	16.4	16.4	16.4
Typhoid	42	10.9	10.9	27.3
Cholera	113	29.4	29.4	56.8
Amoeba	3	.8	.8	57.6
No response	163	42.4	42.4	100.0
Total	384	100.0	100.0	

Source; Field Survey, 2016

Slums/settlements lack adequate physical infrastructure such as accessibility (roads and footpaths), sewer systems, drainage, water and sanitation facilities, electricity and street lighting. Where such facilities exist, they are in a bad state or are results of illegal connections (Mwangi, 1997).

Residents practice open dumping of wastes, private developers once in a while release their sewer into the open drains which flow contaminating water in other areas (See Plate 4.1 and Plate 4.2). Many facilities such as the toilets as seen earlier are communal. This has resulted to a high frequency of illnesses especially Urinary Tract Infections among the children in the slums.

Plate 4.1 Open Dumping And Risky Drains

(Source: Field survey)

Plate 4.2 Sewer In Front Of House

(Source: Field survey)

The Public Health Act of Kenya and its subsidiary rules have detailed standards for housing and sanitation. County Governments are mandated to supervise the enforcement of the law. These county governments also, are expected to establish and maintain sanitary services for the removal and destruction of all kinds of refuse and effluents. However, as the Nairobi City Council Planning Department itself acknowledged to Amnesty International, these laws have never been enforced in relation to Nairobi’s slums and settlements because “these areas are not and have not historically been integrated into the city’s urban plans (Amnesty International, 2009).

The physical geography of Mukuru makes it difficult to access; thus rendering issues of water and sanitation more complex. The swampy soil does not permit the escape of waste water, which then stagnates, consequently contributing to diseases such as cholera, malaria and typhoid fever (Aidah, 2011).

In the new RAP units, 89% have not yet witnessed any disease outbreak, while 6% have actually witnessed (See Figure 4.2). While 4.4% witnessed Malaria cases, 4.2% witnessed cholera cases, 2.3 % had seen typhoid cases while 0.5% reported to have witnessed amoeba cases. Comparing

the two scenarios, it is evident that the cases of disease outbreaks have reduced by far. There is a significant difference between disease outbreaks in the previous and current areas (see Table 4.2). This could be attributed to the better, safer, more hygienic and manageable environment in the RAP units besides other factors i.e. $\chi^2 = (6, N=384) = 106.407, p=0.000$

Table 4.2 Chi-Square Test on Disease Outbreak

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	106.407 ^a	6	0.000
Likelihood Ratio	41.515	6	0.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	102.252	1	0.000
N of Valid Cases	384		

Source; Field Survey, 2016

Figure 4.2 Respondents Who Have Witnessed Disease Outbreaks in the Current Area

Source; Field Survey, 2016

4.1.2 Nearby Health Facilities

Survey findings on health facilities in the current and previous settlements of the respondents (in the study areas) are as shown in Figure 4.3. The nearest health facility for residents of Mbotela and Soweto East is the Public Health Centre, whereas Dispensary is the current nearest health facility for residents of Kianda and Makongeni. Comparing the two areas (previous and current

residences) there is a significant difference between the nearby health facilities in either set ups, $\chi^2= 131.345$, $p=0.000$ (see Table 4.3).

Table 4.3 Chi-Square Tests On Nearby Health Facilities

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	131.345 ^a	16	0.000
Likelihood Ratio	163.512	16	0.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	4.746	1	0.029
Number of Valid Cases	384		

Source; Field Survey, 2016

Depending on the condition of the illness, the PAPs determine where to go to. In the case of serious illness, most opt to go to public health centers nearby such as Makadara Hospital and Kaloleni Hospital, while other manageable illnesses are taken to the local dispensaries and chemists.

The RAP units are strategically situated, being served by major feeder roads of the city. In Soweto East, Mbagathi Hospital and Kenyatta National Hospitals which are public hospitals are relatively nearer and more easily accessible. Apparently, these hospitals are cheaper and from the discussions also, these hospitals offer good services. In the rest, there is a mix in terms of nearby health care choices where respondents acquire medical care.

Also it is noteworthy to note that in the current residences of Kianda and Soweto East, there exist no minority groups that acquire informal health care. From the discussions in Soweto, it's because of waived medical services such as Antenatal Care have been made free in the Kenyan public hospitals.

Figure 4.3 Nearby Health Facility

Source; Field Survey, 2016

4.1.3 State of the Health facilities

On the state of these facilities, it is clear that there is a significant difference between the previous and current health facilities, $\chi^2 = (16, N=384) = 382.408, p=0.000$ (see Table 4.4).

Table 4.4 Chi-Square Test on the Views Concerning the State Of The Health Facilities

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	382.408 ^a	16	.000
Likelihood Ratio	239.124	16	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	206.760	1	.000
No. of Valid Cases	384		

Source; Field Survey, 2016

From Figure 4.4, it is evident that about 13.8% viewed their previous health facilities as ‘not good at all’, 38.3% viewed them to be ‘fair’, 34.9% viewed them to be ‘good’ whilst another 8.9% viewed them to be very good.

Figure 4.4: Views on the State of the Previous Health Facility

Source; Field Survey, 2016

Currently, 22.4% of the PAPs view health facilities to be fair, 52.9% view it to be good, while 17.7% view it to be very good (see Figure 4.5). As from an earlier excerpt in this dissertation, several medical care services in the Kenyan public hospitals have been waived off of their charges. As such, patients are treated freely. Since this is recent, and having occurred at the same time when the PAPs are being moved into the new houses, this could also account for these views.

Notwithstanding this, as it has been denoted elsewhere, environmental improvements are important in improvement of health status (Gulis, Mulumba, Juma, & Kakosova, 2004). Perhaps due to reduction of the cases of illnesses in the PAP units, the PAPs are easily attended to at the hospitals when ill. As such, it is important to associate the environmental improvements with the relatively good views of medical care services.

Figure 4.5 Views on the State of the Current Health Facility

Source; Field Survey, 2016

4.2 Energy

4.2.1 Source of energy for cooking and heating

In their previous areas before, it is clear that majority used to use Charcoal (71.1%) and Paraffin (26.6%) as their main sources of energy, followed by LPG (20.2%) (See Table 4.4 and Table 4.5).

Seemingly life in the different slums does not really vary, because slums residents across board suffer similar wants and needs. Across Mukuru slum where most PAPs at Makongeni and Mbotela relocated from, and across Kibera slum where PAPs in Kianda and Soweto East relocated from, people exclusively used to use charcoal i.e. 67.7% (Kianda PAPs), 85.6% (Makongeni), 74.1% (Mbotela) and 66.1% (Soweto East) (See Figure 4.6). From this survey, it is evident that charcoal is extensively used followed by LPG. Firewood, in the RAP units, are not being used any more.

Table 4.5: Previous Source(s) of Energy

S/No.	Source of Energy	Responses	
		No.	Percent
1	Electricity	13	4.0%
2	Charcoal	229	71.1%
3	Firewood	15	4.7%
4	LPG	65	20.2%
Total		322	100.0%

Source; Field Survey, 2016

Table 4.6 Other Previous Source of Energy

	Frequency	%	Valid %	Cumulative Percent
No response	282	73.4	73.4	73.4
Stove	102	26.6	26.6	100.0
Total	384	100.0	100.0	

Source; Field Survey, 2016

Figure 4.6 Source of Energy for the Respondents In Both Previous And Current Residence

Source; Field Survey, 2016

In slum areas of Nairobi, charcoal is sold out commercially in sacks. Some respondents, both in Mukuru and Kibera, used to use LPG for cooking. From the focused group discussions, it was determined that the use of LPG had been embraced due to the high cases of fire incidences as a result of the use of stoves, and firewood in the slums, which are characteristically vulnerable to

fire spread. Stove accidents, ended up burning the entire structures including the neighboring ones causing a lot of damage and loss of property.

In Kenya, Provision of energy is controlled by government owned firms. Since Kibera settlements are classified as illegal, these energy firms have not been able to set power transmission points in many parts of the slum (Mutisya and Yarime, 2011). As such, the slum structure owners/ landlords have set up their own illegal power connections (see Plate 4.3 and Plate 4.4) to serve their structures, also acting as sources of income for them. Due to high costs of electric lighting, it's used by slum residents generally for lighting purposes.

Plate 4.3 Illegal Electricity Connections in Mukuru Sinai

(Source: Field survey)

Plate 4.4 Illegal Electricity Connections In Soweto East,
(Source: Field survey)

Table 4.7 Current Overall Source of Energy

Source of Energy	Responses	
	Number	Percent
Electricity	13	4.2%
Charcoal	193	62.1%
LPG	105	33.8%
Total	311	100.0%

Source; Field Survey, 2016

Table 4.8 Other Source of Energy Being Used Currently

Other source of energy	Frequency	Percent	Percent	Cumulative Percent
No response	268	69.8	69.8	69.8
Stove	116	30.2	30.2	100.0
Total	384	100	100	

Source; Field Survey, 2016

Currently in the RAP units, 62.1% of the respondents use charcoal for cooking, 33.8% of the respondents use LPG while 30.2% use Paraffin (see Table 4.7

Table 4.7 4.8). There is a significant difference between the source of energy for cooking or heating in the two areas $\chi^2 = (20, N=384) = 102.487, p=0.000$. See Table 4.9.

Table 4.9 Chi-Square Test on Source of Energy for Cooking and Heating

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	102.487 ^a	20	0.000
Likelihood Ratio	96.402	20	0.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	8.908	1	0.003
N of Valid Cases	384		

Source; Field Survey, 2016

Comparison with Table 3.21 and 4.6 shows that there is a slight drop in terms of charcoal usage from 71.1%. PAPs have also considered shifting to the use of LPG, from 20.2% to 33.8%, and also to Paraffin from 26.6% to 30.2%. As earlier stated, firewood is no longer a source of energy. There is therefore a tendency towards cleaner sources of energy. Initially only 4.2% had access to electricity but currently its 4.8%, a relatively small increase. Otherwise, the process of installing electricity in every house is ongoing.

Since charcoal is much cheaper as compared to the other sources, most of the PAPs consider using it for heating and cooking. It is much accessible and also easy to use. Again, they still use Paraffin, which is quicker to use, and the small increase in the percentage could be attributed to the fact that the units that they live inside are no more vulnerable to fire instances unlike in their previous residences in the slum area.

In all cases withstanding, there is a noteworthy shift from the use of firewood for cooking and heating from the results, so that PAPs currently are tending to an energy mix of charcoal- LPG- Stove. Even so, they used to use charcoal and LPG, but there again there is a noticeable increment in terms of LPG usage (see Figure 3.22). LPG is convenient, fast, and reliable. It is usable in all seasons unlike charcoal and is clean generally. Although electricity is being installed in every house, they might not end up using it for cooking because the cost of electricity is generally high and as identified by Mutisya and Yarime (2011), the cost is also high for other residents in Nairobi.

4.3 Security

In both areas withstanding, previous and current, it was evident that police posts exist. According to 61.2% of the respondents, their previous area was completely not secure at all. While 20.6% viewed the area to be fairly secure, 11.2% found it secure and a minority 3.6% found it to be very secure (see Figure 4.7).

From the FGDs, some of the slum residents had grouped themselves in a ‘*Nyumba kumi Initiative*’. In this project, a small number of households come together, contribute some money, construct a gate point to their houses and enforce security either through employing security personnel or just locking the gate where every household is entitled to a key to the gate. Others employ Maasai men who are well known for their security expertise and then pay them daily/ monthly as agreed. Even so, Adopt a light Initiative that was set up in 2002, together with the 2005 UN-Habitat Slum Lighting Project have really helped in lighting up both Mukuru and Kibera slums at night hence improving security in these areas.

Figure 4.7 Level of Security in the Previous Area

Source; Field Survey, 2016

Comparing previous (see Figure 4.7) and current security conditions (see Figure 4.8), it is evident that 47.7% attest that their current area is secure, according to 25.5%, it is very secure whereas only 6.0% felt that their new area is not secure (see Figure 4.8). The better security condition in the new area(s) would be attributed to secured entry points (having one or two

entrances). And as such with the lack of many access points, security check becomes relatively easier.

Figure 4.8 Level of Security in the Current Residence

Source; Field Survey, 2016

Figure 4.9 Current Level of Security

Source; Field Survey, 2016

At Kianda segment, majority respondents, 46.8%, reported that their area is very secure, 37.7% reported that their area is secure while according to 10.4% it was fairly secure (see Figure 4.9). Like Soweto East, a similar experience occurs where according to 38.0% the area is very secure, according to 49.4% it is secure, while according to 11.4% its fairly secure. Figuratively, these two segments have similar characteristics of having only one access point to the units. At the access point, there are security personnel, who interchangeably work during the day and night.

At Mbotela, 21.2% reported that their area to be very secure, 48.7% reported that their area is secure while 19.5% reported that the area is fairly secure. There are two access points to these units and both access points have security personnel guarding. PAPs in this area benefit from the Adopt a Light project whose mast lights up part of the neighborhood.

At Makongeni, only 7.0% view their area to be very secure, 52.2% find their area secure, 22.6% of the PAPs find their area to be fairly secure while according to 17.4% their area is not secure. These units have open ungated accesses used by both PAPs, and passers-by. In addition to this, the units lack a fence and as such faces a threat of security although they have security personnel.

Generally, it is evident from the results that the level of security has actually increased.

4.3.1 Accessibility of Locality

In their previous setup, generally 87% of the respondents reported to have had no challenges of accessing their localities while 8% had challenges (see Figure 4.10).

Of those that had challenges (see Figure 4.11), 2.1% reported that it were due to lack of adequate development control mechanisms. For instance, there is no area zoned out for waste dumping, as such, roads serve as dumping areas, including any open spaces. During the rainy seasons, wastes block the free flow of water resulting to dumping instances, hence roads impassability. A group of 9.1% reported that inaccessibility was due to poor drainage problems (See Plate 4.4), while 3.6% reported that it was due to a lack of access road and had to follow the rail road to their houses. Consequently, due to the lack of access roads, residents were forced to walk for long distances so as to access the main road (see Plate 4.5 and Plate 4.6).

Figure 4.10 Respondents Who Had Problem of Accessing Their Previous Locality

Source; Field Survey, 2016

Figure 4.11 Reasons Of Inaccessibility in Both Previous And Current Locality

Source; Field Survey, 2016

Plate 4.5 Poor Road Accessibility Due To Poor Drainage

(Source: Field survey)

Plate 4.6 Inadequate Dev. Control Mechanisms, Waste Dumping

(Source: Field survey)

As observed by Amnesty International (2009), roads within Nairobi’s informal settlements (the current study area being no exception) are often narrow and impassable during the rainy seasons. This has subsequently proved a great restriction for these areas to be served with government services for example emergency health care services, drainage installation and repair, fire emergency services, security services among others. There is a significant difference between the previous and current areas in terms of accessing the locality $\chi^2 = (24, N=384) = 297.692, p=.000$ (see Table 4.10).

Table 4.10 Chi-Square Test on Accessibility of Locality

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	297.692 ^a	24	0.000
Likelihood Ratio	102.580	24	0.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	22.173	1	0.000
Number of Valid Cases	384		

In the current area, 93.8% reported to have no hindrances as to access their locality. Only 3.4% face the challenge of a lack of adequate development control mechanisms, 0.8% faces the challenge of poor drainage while 2.1% faced the challenge of a lack of access road (see Figure 4.11). The lack of the access road realistically would emanate only within the units because of its longevated design with limited access point. Without, the Public road networks are nearby, efficient, and effective.

4.4 Fire Services

As earlier stated, approximately 60% of the Nairobi’s population live in the slums which form only 5% of the land. The city’s overcrowded slums and informal settlements, whose structures are constructed from cheap and wobbly materials like corrugated iron and connected to hazardous illegal electricity lines, make them particularly vulnerable to fire (UN-HABITAT, 2010). As noted earlier also, the access roads are few and congested making passage difficult for fire trucks.

According to UN-Habitat (2010), data shows that the triggers of fires in majority of the cases are unknown, ranging from stove explosions, electrical circuit failure, left over burning cigarette sticks, and unattended candles.

It has also been noted that most fire incidents happen during seasons of high temperatures and dry conditions which when accompanied by strong winds wafting the flames, the severity and extent of the fire is increased. Most fires take place at night, attesting to the delayed response, compounded with problems of proper access road for fire service vehicles, limited availability of water and rising levels of panic and disorders all hampering response activities (Ruth, 2014).

In the previous area, there were several cases of fire outbreaks. From Table 4.11, 49% of the respondents reported that cases of fire outbreak were unpredictable, 25% said they were annual, according to 13.3% they were monthly, while according to 6.3% these cases were weekly.

Table 4.11 Overall Previous Cases of Fire Outbreaks

	Frequency (%)	Percent (%)	Valid Percent (%)	Cumulative Percent (%)
Weekly	24	6.3	6.3	6.3
Monthly	51	13.3	13.3	19.5
Annually	96	25.0	25.0	44.5
Irregular/Unpredictable	188	49.0	49.0	93.5
No response	25	6.5	6.5	100.0
Total	384	100.0	100.0	

Source; Field Survey, 2016

Statistically, there is a significant difference between the cases of fire outbreak in the previous and the current setups, $\chi^2 = (20, N=384) = 98.064, p=0.000$ (see Table 4.12).

Table 4.12 Chi-Square Test on Cases of Fire Outbreak

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	98.064 ^a	20	.000
Likelihood Ratio	101.744	20	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	48.070	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	384		

Source; Field Survey, 2016

There is a general reduction of fire cases across the RAP segments. In Mbotela and Soweto East, no case of fire has been experienced. The likelihood of fire outbreaks are highly unpredictable more so in the current area. This could be attributed largely to the better stone structures that are fire resistant, and proper electricity connections (see Plate 4.7 and Plate 4.8). Unlike the previous residence, the strategic location of the RAP units makes them to be easily accessible. The roads

have proper drainage and are furnished with security lights which would definitely boost accessibility in a fire instance.

Plate 4.7 A Power Meter for a Single Unit

Source: RAP Files, 2014

Plate 4.8 Power Board.

Source: RAP Files, 2014

4.5 Preservation

Woodley Social Hall has been identified as the only recreation base and public facility that is within the Kibera neighborhood. Most open spaces which could have been used for recreational purposes within the neighborhood are either swampy, irregularly allocated to private developers or are used as dumping grounds (Romanus and Oyugi, 2010). Due to this challenge, the development of social facilities in the locality has been greatly affected. Recreational grounds and areas reserved for community facilities such as markets, schools, mosques and churches have also become targets for informal sector activities locations (Ruth, 2014). In both situations (Mukuru and Kibera), there exists libraries and sport facilities (see Figure 4.12 and 4.13).

Figure 4.12 Recreational Facilities in the Previous Area

Source; Field Survey, 2016

Even after the relocation, not many changes occur. In Kianda, respondents reported that their nearest library was in Community area in both situations. Olympic ground is the nearest public open grounds for Kianda residents where they hold their public meetings, rallies and campaigns. (see Table 4.13 and Table 4.14). From Table 4.13, most of the respondents in either previous/current state do not use these facilities for recreation i.e. 35.1% in Kianda, and 60.8% in Soweto East (from Kibera), and 44.3% in Makongeni and 53.1% in Mbotela (from Mukuru).

Figure 4.13: Recreational Facilities in the Current Residence

Source; Field Survey, 2016

Table 4.13 Views on Recreational Facilities in the Previous Areas

S/No.	State of Facilities	Kianda		Makongeni		Mbotela		Soweto East		Total	
		#	%	#	%	#	%	#	%	#	%
1	Very Good	7	9.1%	3	2.6%	3	2.7%	3	3.8%	16	4.2%
2	Good	18	23.4%	21	18.3%	9	8.0%	10	12.7%	58	15.1%
3	Fair	22	28.6%	12	10.4%	26	23.0%	12	15.2%	72	18.8%
4	Not good at all	3	3.9%	28	24.3%	15	13.3%	6	7.6%	52	13.5%
5	No response	27	35.1%	51	44.3%	60	53.1%	48	60.8%	186	48.4%
Total		77	100.0	115	100%	113	100%	79	100%	384	100%

Source; Field Survey, 2016

Table 4.14 Views on Recreational Facilities in the Current Areas

S/No.	State of Facilities	Kianda		Makongeni		Mbotela		Soweto East		Total	
		#	%	#	%	#	%	#	%	#	%
1	Very Good	7	9.1%	4	3.5%	10	8.8%	14	17.7%	35	9.1%
2	Good	19	24.7%	23	20.0%	20	17.7%	8	10.1%	70	18.2%
3	Fair	15	19.5%	16	13.9%	17	15.0%	4	5.1%	52	13.5%
4	Not good at all	2	2.6%	20	17.4%	3	2.7%	1	1.3%	26	6.8%
5	No response	34	44.2%	52	45.2%	63	55.8%	52	65.8%	201	52.3%
Total		77	100.0%	115	100.0%	113	100.0%	79	100.0%	384	100.0%

Source; Field Survey, 2016

There is a however a significant difference between the views of respondents concerning the recreational facilities in both the previous and current scenarios (see Table 4.15),

$$\chi^2 = (20, N=384) = 446.751, p=0.000.$$

Table 4.15 Chi-Square Tests on Preservation

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	446.751 ^a	20	.000
Likelihood Ratio	367.338	20	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	183.738	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	384		

Source; Field Survey, 2016

Those who were using these facilities especially for sport purposes were men. Women reported during the FGDs that they were busy carrying out home chores, and doing businesses to earn a

living. In addition to this, women were afraid to use some of these facilities on a usual day due to reasons of insecurity. At night, homeless people, street urchins and thugs find shelter in these areas, and usually cause lot of harm to people visiting.

From the FGDs, in the previous area, children were not going to the public open grounds rather they used to play along the roads or wherever they could space(see Appendix 2). Again in both cases children benefit from the nearby public schools around that have playgrounds in addition to the spaces that are outside the RAP units (see Plate 4.9).

Although preservation efforts for recreation were not part of the aims of the RAP project, there are slightly better views concerning the open space facilities. From the discussions, this would largely be associated to the fact that children are currently using the space outside the units for playing, which is much safer than on the road where they previously used to play in. Again, the open grounds currently are much more accessible by their users than in the previous residences.

Plate 4.9 Children Playing Outside the RAP Units

Source; Field Survey, 2016

4.6 Environmental Awareness

Of the total respondents, only 41% responded that in their previous area they had sensitization towards their environment compared to 79% in the current residences (see Figure 4.14 and Figure 4.15). From Table 4.16, it is evident that about 25.1% of the respondents reported that information on environmental issues was being passed through the use of posters, 6.8% through rallies, 16.8% through mass media, 39.4% got through segment leaders while 11.8% obtained such information through health officials from the City County. In the current area of residences, the use of segment leaders and posters respectively also serve as the major tools of relaying and propagating environmental issues to the residents (see Table 4.17).

Table 4.16 Previous Media of Information on Environmental Issues

S/No.	Media	Responses	
		No.	Percent
1	Posters	70	25.1%
2	Rallies	19	6.8%
3	Mass Media	47	16.8%
4	Segment Leaders	110	39.4%
5	City County	33	11.8%
Total		279	100.0%

Source; Field Survey, 2016

Figure 4.14 Respondents Sensitized on Environmental Issues

Source; Field Survey, 2016

Figure 4.15 : Percent (%) of Respondents informed on Environmental Sensitization in the Previous Residence

Source; Field Survey, 2016

Table 4.17 Current Media for Environmental Sensitization

S/No.	Media	Responses	
		No.	Percent
1	Posters	85	20.9%
2	Rallies	21	5.2%
3	Mass Media	64	15.8%
4	Segment Leaders	181	44.6%
5	County Council	55	13.5%
Total		406	100.0%

Source; Field Survey, 2016

Before the operation phase of the RAP project, some of the PAPs to be and their leaders were invited for a briefing on how the process of RAP would unfold. It was a presentation series with projections on the design of the units and the aftermath life in the RAP units. Residents were involved in the selection of preferable relocation sites but this was not implemented due to other political conditions that prevailed. Many have benefited from RAP Construction by obtaining employment from the contractors. Health officials from the Ministry of Health were involved at the onset of getting into the houses. These addressed issues on sanitation and hygiene to the PAPs, to ensure that the environment is clean, decent and habitable.

From the above research findings, it is evident (see Table 4.18) that there is a significant difference in terms of the availability of information as pertaining environmental management between the previous and the current areas of residence i.e. $\chi^2 = (25, N=384)=277.290, p=0.000$

Table 4.18 Chi-Square Test on Availability of Information for Environmental Sensitization

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	277.290 ^a	25	0.000
Likelihood Ratio	219.531	25	0.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	15.017	1	0.000
N of Valid Cases	384		

Source; Field Survey, 2016

The PAPs currently have a heightened sense of obligation towards protecting their environment. Unlike in the informal settlements where they used to live before, more information as pertaining to environment management is relayed to them, through their segment heads and other forms of media.

CHAPTER FIVE

5. SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter provides the summary of the dissertation, its verdict as reinstated in the conclusions, and finally the recommendations that could be employed to foster UR strategies that are environmentally sustainable.

5.1 Summary

Cities are hosting more people than the rural areas currently more than before. Over the years this has led to the growth of unplanned settlements that are characterized by general urban decay especially in Africa and Asia. The world is experiencing a new dynamic wave of urban renewal, to cope up with the challenge of rapid urbanization rates. According to this research, a quest for effective environmental management thereto is thus inevitable for sustainability reasons. In regard to this, the dissertation's objective was to assess whether UR is an effective tool for environmental management.

In different parts of the world, different strategies of Urban renewal have been implemented and Nairobi County, Kenya is not an exceptional. In this city, these projects have ranged from redevelopment projects, housing improvements, streetscape improvements, transport enhancement, to historic preservation projects and exercises.

This project set out to find out whether there is a significant difference in the environment before and after the implementation of UR Strategies, where The RAP project of The Kenya Railways Corporation formed the sample sites.

5.1.1 Socio-economic, Housing and Basic Urban Environmental Characteristics.

The project largely encompassed people in the middle age bracket, majority being less than 45 years of age but above 26 years of age. From the results its evident that 10.7 % were between 41 and 45, 10.9 % were between 36 and 40 years, 17.2 % were between 31 and 35, while 26.6 % were between 26 and 30 years of age.

Due to the nature of the RAP houses after relocation to the RAP houses, some families were forced to reorganize themselves so as to live comfortably in these houses. From the FGDs, the

younger families and those that were initially few occupants benefited much more than them that were many in the same household. Large families that lived in one /two/ three bedroomed houses had to find other options for shelter in other parts of the slum away from the railway reserve or elsewhere (see appendix 2).

There is a significant difference in terms of the sources of water between the previous and the current residence i.e. $\chi^2 (30, N=384) = 176.795, p=0.000$. Currently, 70.2% of the residents obtain water from the city council. RAP units has every of its units connected to a water meter, construing that they shall finally be accessing water from inside their units as opposed to buying water from the local water vendors.

Generally in both situations, there seems to be a persistent challenge of water availability. Statistical analysis depict that there is actually no significant difference between the two accounts of residence $t (383) = 0.516, p=0.606$. The RAP project apportioned every unit a water tank however residents have had to develop further coping mechanisms including acquiring more water tanks and basins to boost water storage. Although this could be due to technical bearing in the RAP project, water rationing in the informal settlements of Nairobi are also high, even as some of the connections are actually illegal.

Again, there is no significant difference between the two scenarios, in terms of water payment $t (383) = - 0.171, p=0.864$. In both cases, the water bills do not vary. Of the 31% that responded on their previous payment scenario, approximately 28.2% reported to have been paying between 101 and 1000 KES. Currently, 88.9% reported that they pay between 101 and 1000 KES even on top of the flat rate of 200 KES.

In the current area, the location of a PAP's house would determine accessibility to different limited facilities among which water is one of them. On this variable, this discussion looks at the two facets attached to it. First, the RAP units are long being served with two exits which also serve as the segment entrances except for the case of Makongeni that is exceptional because it lacks a fence / a partitioning structure. This makes it difficult to access water during the water rationing instances. In the slum, lesser distances are covered to obtain water due to the availability of unlimited access paths. Secondly, every RAP unit is currently entitled to a water meter, and upon solving the technical issues, the residents shall readily obtain water in their units

unlike in the slums. In either scenarios of water accessibility, this study argues that there is a significant difference in terms of distance covered.

The market conditions have improved, so that they are cleaner and well-ordered than in the previous account. Infact, there is a significant difference between the market condition in the previous and current situations $\chi^2 (16, N=384) = 254.403, p=.000$.

There is also no significant difference between the previous and current distances covered in a bid to access their nearest retail shops i.e. $t (25) = 253.6, p=0.464$. Even so, some of the PAPs prefer to go to the market places that they used to go before relocation while others have had to cope with the new area, opting to go to the nearby markets.

From the above table, there is a significant difference between the methods of waste collection in the two accounts $\chi^2 = (20, N=384) = 161.342, p= 0.000$. Currently, 85.4 % reported that waste is majorly disposed by private collectors who are hired by the PAPs themselves who pay KES 500 towards garbage collection and security services within the RAP units. Initially majority of the PAPs, 54.4%, used to dump waste on the railway tracks and land. Currently it is well impossible due to the design of the RAP units that are elongated and built facing away from the railway reserve and with no entry point into the railway reserve. Whereas in the previous residence few had their waste being collected once per week/ daily, currently majority have their waste being collected once or twice a week.

Majority of the residents prefer current waste collection i.e. 44% reported that it was good while according to 18% waste collection was very good. Apart from the environment of the RAP units being sight friendly, the PAPs are already appreciating an environment that is friendly for them to live and stay and for children to play.

In the current set up, all houses have been allocated with a flushing closet, furnished with a water cistern that is connected to a proper sewer system that is functionally efficient. A storm sewer drain has also been provided to trap running water from the pavement and the neighbourhood, thus inhibiting the stagnation of water.

5.1.2 Health, Energy, Security, Environmental Awareness Of The Residents, And Fire Attributes Of The Area.

There is a significant difference between disease outbreaks in the previous and current areas, i.e. $\chi^2 = (6, N=384) = 106.407, p=0.000$. Diseases have drastically reduced because every household in the current set up have their own facilities. As such, management of these utilities by households has become much easier and tolerable, compounded by the proper system of waste disposal and generally cleaner environments.

With closer proximity to the public hospitals, compounded by the strategic locations of the RAP units, it is relatively easier to obtain medical services. Generally, public hospitals are preferred though, even because of their free or fair charges compounded with their high level medical expertise found in them.

Currently in the RAP units, 62.1% of the PAPs use charcoal for cooking, 33.8% use LPG while 30.2% use paraffin as their sources of energy. Previously, 71.1% of the respondents used Charcoal, 26.6% used paraffin, while 20.2% used LPG as their main sources of energy. There is a noteworthy shift from the use of firewood for cooking and heating from the results, so that PAPs currently are tending to an energy mix of charcoal- LPG- Stove. Even so, they used to use charcoal and LPG, but there again there is a noticeable increment in terms of LPG usage. Clearly there is a general shift towards the use of cleaner sources of energy.

Security level has increased in the current residence. This is evident from the results where 61.2% of the respondents reported that their previous residence were not secure and only 3.6 viewed the previous situation to be secure. Currently, 47.7% reported that their residence is secure while 25.5% others reported that their current residence is very secure.

There is a significant difference between the cases of fire outbreak in the previous and the current setups, $\chi^2 = (20, N=384) = 98.064, p=0.000$. There is a general reduction of fire cases across the RAP segments. In Mbotela and Soweto East, no case of fire has been experienced. The likelihood of fire outbreaks are highly unpredictable more so in the current area. This could be attributed largely to the better stone structures that are fire resistant, and proper electricity connections

Fire outbreaks have reduced drastically, arguably due to the structural condition of the building which besides being fire resistant, they are also resistant to harsh weather conditions. The strategic location of the RAP project makes them to be easily accessible. The roads have proper drainage and security lights, which besides making them even more accessible; have increased the security levels of these areas than their previous areas in the informal settlements.

There are slightly better views concerning the open space facilities. From the discussions, this would largely be associated to the fact that children are currently using the space outside the units for playing, which is much safer than on the road where they previously used to play. Again, the open grounds currently are much more accessible by their users than in the previous residences.

The PAPs currently have a heightened sense of obligation towards protecting their environment. Unlike in the informal settlements where they used to live before, information as pertaining to environment management is relayed to them. In regard to this, 79% in the current residence as opposed to 41% in the previous residence reported that they do obtain information on environmental sensitization. This is majorly done by segment heads and other forms of media.

5.2 Conclusions

The above discussions however, confirm part of the research's original expectations. This is clearly depicted from the results where some characteristics portrayed a significant difference between the previous and the current state whereas others did not. The project completely changed all the PAPs lives, from the slum setting to the current RAP settings where the environment is cleaner and friendlier. Future action should entail proper technical expertise to prevent general utility breakdowns for the project affected persons where possible.

Conclusively, Urban renewal that is smartly effected, is a tool for environmental management. It has an unwavering potential of bringing life to decaying and decayed cities and places. The implication of this is that, UR strategies should be implemented in view of environmental considerations for them to be environmentally sustainable. These results should infer mitigation actions and behaviors for intended UR project implementation as argued by Stern's VBN Theory adopted by this dissertation.

5.3 Recommendations

There ought to be an increased awareness of Urban Renewal concept in Kenya, and its potential to manage the environment. The government should build an Urban Renewal authority that is cross- sectoral so as to reinforce UR and the general cadre of urban development effectively. The RAP project and the findings of this research can be replicated in other urban development projects successfully.

Urban Renewal as an urban development program is urgently required for Kenya's cities and towns in a bid to eliminate blight, as a result of the country's rapid urbanization rate. From this research, it is evident that UR effectively implemented can be used to manage the negative effects of urban decay.

Tested Best Practices should be adopted while implementing UR programs. To manage all the urban environmental characteristics favorably, a judicially coordinated multi-sectoral approach needs to be adopted ensuring that the program is more participatory in nature involving the affected persons broadly. In addition to this, incentives to shape attitude and behavior can be introduced so as to boost environmental management best practices.

An Effective Assistance Paradigm entailing three complementary building blocks should be the foundation for UR. These include;

5.3.1. Policy Reform.

Nairobi City County should set pace in creating a policy document for Urban Renewal Projects. This is because the city is worst affected as compared to the other Kenyan cities, which also are at risk of decay. The policy document should have an environmental sustainability guide to ensure that projects are consistent with environmental management. Some of these policies and reforms should include;

1. Protection of the mandate, and goals of UR Authorities in the country.
2. Identification and review of areas designated for redevelopment, rehabilitation, clearance and conservation,

3. Location, extent and scope of UR projects including the identification of procedures for undertaking them,
4. Provision of environmental sustainability checks that guide UR projects,
5. The mandatory submission of Environmental Impact Assessment and Environmental Assessment reports before the commissioning phase.

5.3.2 Urban Planning.

City development plans should be developed in conjunction with different stakeholders. The public should be involved during the planning process. The role of urban planners is key so that a redevelopment, rehabilitation strategy, clearance strategy, or a conservation strategy creates positive impact on the urban environment.

5.3.3 Host Country Ownership.

Even with help and assistance from donors and the international community generally, the host country should own its problems and challenges of decay or environmental degradation and offer full national government support, county support and inclusive affected persons' participation. It should check into the completion of the project to ensure that the project is actually completed before it is commissioned.

5.3.4 Research Gaps

Future gaps should focus on the future aspect of environmentally sustainable UR strategies as well as an in-depth view of other sustainability paradigms of UR.

REFERENCES

- ISO 14001. (2015). *Environmental Management Systems - Requirements with guidance for use* (3rd ed.). Geneva, Switzerland: ISO.
- Achola, M. (2002). "Colonial policy and urban health: The case of colonial Nairobi," In A. B. (ed.), *The Urban Experience in Eastern Africa c. 1750-2000*. (pp. pp. 119-137). Nairobi: British Institute in Eastern Africa.
- Adams, D., and Hastings, E. M. (2001). "Urban renewal in Hong Kong: Transition from development corporation to renewal authority," *Land use Policy*, 18(3), 245-258.
- Adiabokpa, P., Alalade A. O., Aremu A. B., Ibiyemi A. E., and Ojo B. (2012). Appraisal of Urban Renewal Projects in Osun State. Retrieved from <https://www.academia.edu/8458180/>
- Agbola, T. (1987). "Institutional constraints on housing development: The urban areas of Nigeria: The Land-Use Decree and The Building Plan Approval Process." *Habitat International*, 11(2), 113-120.
- Aidah, B. (2011). *Umande Trust Bio-Centre Approach in Slum Upgrading*. Nairobi: Les cahiers d'Afrique de l'Est, IFRA.
- Aluko, B., and Amidu, A. R. (2006). "Urban low income settlements, land deregulation and sustainable development in Nigeria." *5th FIG Regional Conference: Promoting Land Administration and Good Governance* (pp. 1-12.). Accra, Ghana: FIG.
- Amendah, D. D., Buigut, S., and Mohamed, S. (2014). "Coping Strategies among Urban Poor: Evidence from Nairobi, Kenya." (S. Molyneux, Ed.) *Open Access*, 9(1).
- Amnesty International. (2009). *Kenya's The Unseen Majority- Nairobi's Two Million Slum-dwellers*. Peter Benenson House, 1 Easton Street, London, United Kingdom: Amnesty International Publications International Secretariat.
- Anderson, M. (1964). "A critical analysis of Urban Renewal 1949-1962," In *The Federal Bulldozer* (pp. 65-67). Cambridge: The M.I.T Press.
- Anke, K. (2009). "South Africa Urban Renewal Programmes (URP). Development of Rural/Urban nodes in the context of migration," *Conference: Urban-Rural Linkages and Migration*. GFA Consulting Group.

- Annez, P. C., and Buckley, R. M. (2009). "Urbanization and Growth: Setting the Context," In M. Spence, P. C. Annez and R. M. Buckley (Eds.), *Urbanization and growth. Commission on growth and development* (pp. 1-45). Washington, DC: The World Bank.
- APHRC. (2012). "Population and Health Dynamics in Nairobi's Informal Settlements. Report of the Nairobi Cross-sectional Slums Survey (NCSS) 2012," *International Journal of Epidemiology*. (2015) doi: 10.1093/ije/dyu251
- Blevin, C., and Bouczo, J. (1997). "Nairobi: A century of history (1898-1997)," *Cahiers de l'IFRA*, no. 5, 30-53.
- Boedecker, C. (1936). *Early History of Nairobi Township*. Nairobi: MacMillan Library.
- Boundless. (2016, May 26). "Models of Urban Growth." Retrieved on August 24, 2016, from Boundless: <https://www.boundless.com/sociology/textbooks/boundless-sociology-textbook/population-and-urbanization-17/urbanization-and-the-development-of-cities-123/models-of-urban-growth-698-10481/>
- Broudehoux, A. (1994). *Neighbourhood Regeneration in Beijing: An overview of Projects Implemented in the Inner City Since 1990*. McGill. McGill University .
- Broudehoux, A. M. (2005). *Minimum Cost Housing Group*. In N. R. 1990. Canada: McGill University.
- Castells. (1990). *The Shek Kip Mei Syndrome: Economic Development and Public Housing in Hong Kong and Singapore*. London: Pion Limited,.
- CCN. (2007). *City of Nairobi Environmental Outlook*. Nairobi: City Council of Nairobi (CCN).
- Hatch, R. E., (1984). *The Scope of Social Architecture*. New York: Van Nostrand Reinhold Company.
- Chan, E. H., and Yung, E. H. (2008). "Is the Development Control Legal Framework conducive to a Sustainable Dense Urban Development in Hong Kong?" *Pergamon- Elsevier Science Ltd*, 28(3), 409-426.
- COHRE. (2008). *Women, Slums and Urbanisation: Examining the Causes and Consequences*. Geneva, Switzerland: Centre on Housing Rights and Evictions (COHRE).
- Colborn, M. (1963). *The Neighbourhood and Urban Renewal*. New York: National Federation of Settlements and Neighbourhoods Centre.

- Couch, C. (1990). *Urban renewal: Theory and Practice*. London: MacMillan Education Ltd.
- Dodman, D., Barry, D.C., McGranahan, G., and IIED. (2013). *Integrating the Environment in Urban Planning and Management; Key Principles and Approaches for Cities in The 21st Century*. Nairobi: UNON/Publishing Section Services.
- Egunjobi, L. (1997). *Urban Renewal: Issues, Policies, Strategies and Planning*. Ibadan: NISER /CURP URP.
- EMCA. (1999). *Kenya Environmental Management and Coordination Act 1999*. Nairobi: Government of Kenya.
- Emig, S. and Ismail, Z. (1980). "Notes on the urban planning of Nairobi," *The Journal of Housing and the Built Environment*. Copenhagen School of Architecture. Cambridge: MIT Press. ISSN: 1566-4910
- Engelbrecht, C. (2004). "People and Places; An Overview of Urban Renewal," *South African Cities networks and Cities Alliance*. South Africa: Johannesburg.
- Faerstein, E. (1989). "Systems and Displacement in Brazilian Upgrading Projects." *Open House International*.
- Fisher, A., Laing, J. and Stoeckel, J. (1983). "Guidelines for overcoming design problems in family planning operations research." *Mediline* 16(2), 100-105.
- Foran, R. (1950). "Rise of Nairobi: From campsite to city. Phase in the history of Kenya's capital which is soon to receive a royal charter," In *The Crown Colonist*, London: Crown Colonist, pp. 20 (220):161-5
- Freire, E. M., Lall, S., and Leipziger, D. (2014). *Africa's Urbanization: Challenges and Opportunities*. Washington DC: The Growth Dialogue.
- Gaudie, E. (1974). *Cruel Habitations: A History of working class Housing 1780 – 1918*. London: Allen and Unwin.
- GoK. (2009). *National Museums and Heritage Act [Cap 2016 of the Laws of Kenya]*. Nairobi: Government of Kenya.
- GoK. (2010). *The Constitution of Kenya*. Nairobi, Kenya: National Council for Law Reporting with the Authority of the Attorney General.

- Grebler, L. (1964). *Urban Renewal in European Countries; Its Emergence and Potentials*, Pennsylvania: Pennsylvania University Press.
- Group, N. U. (1973). *Metropolitan Growth Strategy Report prepared for the Nairobi City Council*. Nairobi: ETH Studio Basel .
- Gulis, G., Mulumba, J. A., Juma, O., and Kakosova, B. (2004). "Health status of people of slums in Nairobi, Kenya." Department of Health Promotion Research, Ed. *Environmental Research*. 96, 219–227.
- Hake, A. (1977). *African metropolis: Nairobi Self Help City*. London: Chatto and Windus.
- Hardoy, J., Mitlin, D., and Satterthwaite, D. (2003). *Environmental Problems in Third World Cities*. London, Earthscan.
- HKHA. (1988). In *Hong Kong Housing Authority Annual Report 1987-1988*. Retrieved from <http://www.cityu.edu.hk/hkhousing/hkha/members>
- Holcomb, B., and Beauregard, R. (1981). *Revitalising Cities*. Washington: American Association of Geographers.
- HUD. (2012). "Other Real Property Improvements. US Department of Housing and Urban Development (HUD).Retrieved from <http://portal.hud.gov/hudportal/HUD>.
- Ibeakuzie, M. (2002). "Strategies for Affordable Housing Stock Delivery in Nigeria. In O. S. 2004," 18th Inaugural Lecture of Ambrose Alli University Ekpoma, Benin City: Floreat Systems.
- IDB. (1999). "Suggested definition for determining inclusion criteria for projects and non-lending products in the SDS project tracking system and the 1999 annual report on environment and natural resources." Washington DC: IDB
- Irene, W. K., and Jack, M. (2010). *An inventory of the slums in Nairobi*. Nairobi; Pamoja Trust
- Jacobs, J. (1961). *The Death and Life of Great American Cities*. New York: Vintage Books.
- Jan, J. K., Pieter, v. G., Willem, C., and Bart, R. (2001). *Environmental Management: Towards a Conceptual Framework for Environmental Governance and Sustainable Development*. Washington DC: Inter-American Development Bank.
- Johnson, T. (2005). *An overview of Urban Renewal*. Portland, Oregon: Tashman Johnson LLC

- Karanja, S. (2014). *Urban Renewal Strategies for Nairobi, Ngara Area*. Nairobi, Kenya: Unpublished Graduate Thesis, The University of Nairobi.
- Kenya Forest Services. (2014-2017). KFS Strategic Plan 2014-2017., (p. 7).
- Kerlinger, N. F., and Lee, B. H. (1999). *Foundations of Behavioral Research (Quantitative Methods in Research Psychology)* (4th ed). Fort Worth, TX: Harcourt College Publishers,
- Kibera Facts and Information* (2016). Retrieved from Kibera UK Information Website: <http://www.kibera.org.uk/facts-info/> on 07/04/2016.
- Kingsley, O., and Omatson, M. (2010). *Regeneration in the Nigerian Urban Built Environment. Ekpoma*, Nigeria: Ambrose Alli University, P.M.B. 14.
- Kinyoi. (2013). *An assessment of urban decay in Nairobi's Inner City and its implications on Urban Activities: A case study of Kirinyaga Road activity corridor*. Nairobi, Kenya: University of Nairobi.
- Klos, D. (2008). *The History of Nairobi 1900 - 1950s*. Nairobi: ETH Studio Basel.
- KNBS. (2010). *The 2009 Kenya Population and Housing Census*. Nairobi: Kenya National Bureau of Statistics (KNBS).
- KNBS. (2014). *Kenya Facts and Figures 2014*. Nairobi: Kenya National Bureau of Statistics (KNBS).
- KRC. (2015). *Relocation action plan*. Retrieved from Kenya Railways Corporation: <http://krc.co.ke/relocation-action-planon> 02/04/2016
- Laquian, A. (1983). *Basic Housing: Policies for Urban Sites, Services and Shelter in Developing Countries*. Ottawa: International Development Research Center.
- Law Learner's Library. (2013). Laws applicable to Enviroment Conservation in Kenya. Nairobi, Kenya. Retrieved from <http://www.ckadvocates.co.ke/2013/10/laws-applicable-to-enviroment-conservation-in-kenya/>
- Lee, G. K., and Chan, E. H. (2008). "The analytic hierarchy process (AHP) approach for assessment of urban renewal proposals," *Social Indicator Research*, 89(1), 155-168.
- Lichfield, N. (1998). *Economics in Urban Conservation*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

- Lim, W. S. (1983). *Public Housing and Community Development: The Singapore Experience, Mimar 7, Architecture in Development*. Singapore: Reuter's House,
- Longinus, T. (2010). *Managing Urban Sprawls in Cities of the Developing South - The case of Shack/Slum Dwellers International*. Uppsala:Uppsala University
- Lovei, M., and Weiss, C. (1998). *Environmental Management and Institutions in OECD Countries*. Washington: The World Bank.
- Lynch. (1981). *Good City Form*. Cambridge, Massachusetts: The M.I.T. Press.
- Lynch, K. (1960). *The Image of the City*. Cambridge, Massachusetts: The M.I.T. Press.
- Majale, M. (2002). "Tenure Regularisation in Informal Settlements in Nairobi," In V. K. (Eds), *Urban Land Management in Africa* (pp. 267-283). Dortmund: University of Dortmund.
- Mann, D. A. (1984). "Housing in a State of Conflict," In *Tradition and Modernisation in the People's Republic of China. Ekistics* (pp. 349-353).
- Masayo, T., and Holly, K. W. (2014). *Investing in Sustainable Cities; Challenges and Opportunities*. International Development Finance Club.
- Matrix Development Consultants . (1993). *Settlements An Inventory Office of Housing and Urban Development Programmes*, USAID: Arlington
- Medhurst, F., and Parry, L. J. (1969). "Urban Decay," In *An analysis and a Policy*. London: Macmillan.
- Michael, Q. P. (2002). *Qualitative Research and Evaluation Methods* (4th ed.). Thousand Oaks, California: Sage Publications,.
- Miller, J. M. (Ed.). (1959). *New Life for Cities around the World: International Handbook on Urban Renewal*. New York: Books International.
- Mitullah, W. (2002). *Urban Slums Reports: The case of Nairobi*. Nairobi, Kenya: The University of Nairobi.
- Mitullah, W. (2003). *Understanding Slums: Case Studies for the Global Report on Human Settlements, 2003 – The Case of Nairobi*. Nairobi: UN-Habitat.
- Molotch, H. (1976). "The City as a Growth Machine: Toward a Political Economy of Place," *American Journal of Sociology*, 309-332.

- Monirul, I., and Mustaquim. (2014, January). "Socio-Economic Status of Rural Population: An Income Level Analysis," *Asian Academic Research Journal of Multidisciplinary*, 1(24), 98-106.
- Mugenda, O., and Mugenda, A. (1999). *Research Methods: Quantitative and Qualitative Approaches*. Nairobi: Acts Press.
- Mumford, L. (1961). *The City in History*. New York: Hartcourt, Brace and World, Inc.
- Musangi, W. (2003). "Imperial motifs, Architecture and Urban Planning in British Colonial Kenya and India," *Journal of the Society of Architectural Historians*. Vol. 45 No. 2.
- Mutisya, and Yarime. (2009). "Moving towards urban sustainability in Kenya: A framework for integration of environmental, economic, social and governance dimensions," *Sustainability Science*, Vol 9 No.2,
- Mutisya, E., and Yarime, M. (2011). "Understanding the Grassroots Dynamics of Slums in Nairobi: The Dilemma of Kibera Informal Settlements," *Sustainability Science*. Vol 9 No.205. Doi:10.1007/s11625-013-0223-7
- Mutlu, E. (2009). *Criteria for a "Good" Urban Renewal Project: The Case Of Kadifekale Urban Renewal Project (Izmir, Turkey)*. Unpublished Graduate Thesis, Izmir Institute of Technology.
- Mwangi, I. K. (1997, October). "Environment and Urbanization," *Sage Publications*, 9, 141.
- Nairobi City Commission (1985). *Development plan 1984-1988*. Nairobi: Nairobi City Commission.
- Nairobi Urban Study Group. (1973). *Nairobi metropolitan growth strategy report. Volume I: Main report*. Nairobi: Nairobi City Commission.
- Ministry of Public Works. (1996). *Republic of Kenya. National report and plan of action on shelter and human settlements to the second United Nations conference on human settlements*. Istanbul, Turkey: Habitat II
- NCC. (2014). *Nairobi County Integrated Development Plan*. Nairobi: Nairobi City County.
- Nelson, K. (1988). *Gentrification and Distressed Cities: An Assessment of Trends in Intra-metropolitan Migration*. Madison: The University of Wisconsin Press.

- NEMA. (2003). *State of the Environment Report for Kenya, 2003*. Nairobi: National Environment Management Authority (NEMA).
- Nevanlinna, A. K. (1996). *Interpreting Nairobi: The Cultural Study Of Built Forms*. Helsinki: Bibliotheca Historica.
- Ngau, P. (1995). *Informal Settlements in Nairobi Survey of Slums and Squatter Settlements An Inventory of NGOs and CBOs activities, Nairobi NGOs and CBOs activities*. Nairobi. Habitat International 31(1): 87-99 .
- Njoku, C., and Okoro, G. (2014). "Urban renewal in Nigeria; Case Study of Lagos State," *Journal of Environmental Science and Water Resources* ISSN 2277 0704 Vol. 3(7), pp. 145-148
- Nozick, M. (1992). *No Place Like Home: Building Sustainable Communities*. Ottawa: Canadian Council on Social Development.
- Obudho, R. (1987). "Shelter and services of the poor in Nairobi, Kenya," A paper presented to expert group meeting on shelter and services for the poor in Metropolitan Areas. Nagoya, Japan 12-16 January.
- Obudho, R., and Owuor, S. (1991.) "Urbanization and regional planning of metropolitan Nairobi, Kenya," A paper presented at the international conference on big cities of Africa and Latin America. Toulouse, France.
- Oduola, S. (1987). Urban Renewal: Implementation Strategies. In G. Adepoju, O. Femi, and E. Layi, *Urban Renewal in Nigeria*. Ibadan: Nigerian Institute of Social and Economic Research/CURP
- Olima, W. H. (2001). "The Dynamics and Implications of Sustaining Urban Spatial Segregation in Kenya – Experiences from Nairobi Metropolis," *International Seminar on Segregation in the City*. Lincoln Institute of Land Policy, Cambridge.
- Otiso, M. (2005). "Colonial Urbanisation and Urban Management in Kenya," In *African Urban Spaces in Historical Perspective*. New York: University of Rochester Press.
- Rakodi, C. (Ed.). (1997). *The urban challenge in Africa: Growth And Management of its Large Cities*. Shibuya-ku, Tokyo: United Nations University Press.
- RAP Files. (2014) *Microsoft PowerPoint Presentation by Engineer Migwi, REMU*. Nairobi, Kenya: Kenya Railways Corporation

- Richardson, H. (1971). *Urban Economics*. Oxon, UK: Penguin Books Limited.
- Roberts, P. and Sykes, H. (2000). *Urban Regeneration: A handbook*. London: Sage Publications Limited.
- Romanus, O., and Oyugi, M. O. (2010). "The Dialectics Of Sustainable Neighbourhood Development For Nairobi's Kibera Informal Settlement," *The Icfai University Journal of Architecture*, Vol. II No.1,
- Ruth, K. (2014). *Assessing Fire Hazards Reduction Capabilities In Nairobi*; Nairobi, Kenya: Unpublished Graduate Thesis, The University of Nairobi.
- Ryn, V. d., and Calthorpe, P. (1986). *Sustainable Communities: A New Design Synthesis for Cities, Suburbs and Towns*. San Francisco: Sierra Club Books.
- Samuel, O., and Teresa, M. (2003). "Post Independence Development of Nairobi City, Kenya," *Workshop on African capital Cities*. Dakar, Senegal
- Santiago, M. (1975) *Residential Rehabilitation with Special References to Montreal*. Unpublished. Masters Thesis. Montreal: McGill University School of Architecture.
- Sarantakos, S. (2013). *Social Research* (4th ed.). New York: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Schmit-Kallert, E. (1990). "Housing Policies and Squatters' Struggle in South-East Asia." *Ekistics*; 189-213.
- Selltiz, C. et al. (1976). *Research Methods in Social Relations*, (3rd ed.). New York: Holt, Rineltart and Winston.
- Selltiz, C., Jahoda, M., Deutsch, M., and Cook, W. S. (1976). *Research Methods in Social Relations* (3rd ed., Vol. I). New York: Holt, Rineltart and Winston.
- Shihembetsa. (1989). "Urban Developments and Dwelling Environments. Brief Notes on Dandora, Kariobangi and Eastleigh," International Workshop on Housing, KU-Leuven.
- Shinn, D. (1987). Urban Renewal and Management: The American Experience. In G. Adepoju, O. Femi, and E. Layi, *Urban Renewal in Nigeria* (pp. 51-58). Ibadan, Nigeria: Nigerian Institute of Social and Economic Research/CURP.
- Siew-Eng, T. (1989). "Patterns of Change in Public Housing in Singapore," In *Third World Planning Review* (pp. 11 (4) 373-391).

- Situma, F. (1992). "The Environmental Problems in the City of Nairobi," *African Urban Quarterly*, Vol 7 Nos 1 and 2,(1-2), 167-175.
- Spreiregen, P. (1971). "The Modern Metropolis; Its origins, Growth, Characteristics and Planning," In *Selected essays by Hans Blumenfeld*. Cambridge, Mass: The MIT Press.
- Stern, P. C. (2000). Towards a coherent theory of environmentally significant behavior. *Journal of social issues*. 56(31), 497- 424.
- Suzan, P. M. (2010). *The impact of Urban Renewal projects for enhanced sustainable livelihoods in Soweto*. South Africa: Unpublished Graduate Thesis, Vaal Triangle Campus Of North West University.
- Syagga. (2001). *Nairobi Situation Analysis Consultative Report: Collaborative Nairobi Slum Upgrading Initiative*. Nairobi: Government of Kenya and The United Nations Centre for Human Settlements.
- Syagga, P., Winnie, M., and Sarah, G. K. (2001). *Nairobi Situation Analysis A Consultative Report*. Nairobi: Government of Kenya and The United Nations Centre for Human Settlements.
- Tairo, M. (2012). "Why Upgrading of Slums has Flopped," *Star Newspaper*, 20th March 2012 Accessed On 21st February 2014.
- Tetlow, and Goss. (1968). *Home, Towns and Traffic*. London: Faber and Faber.
- Tiwari, R. (1981). "The origin, growth and the functional structures of Central Business District (CBD) of Nairobi," In R. Obudho, (ed) *Urbanization and Development Planning in Kenya*. Nairobi: Kenya Literature Bureau. pp 123-40
- Umande Trust. (2007). *The Right to Water and Sanitation in Kibera in Nairobi*. Nairobi: Umande Trust.
- Umberto, P., Lisa, L., Berger, G., and Hametne, M. (2015). *The Sustainable Development Goals and their Impact on The European SDG Governance Structure; Preparing for the Post-2015 Agenda*. Europe: European Sustainable Development Network (ESDN).
- UN. (2006). *The Millenium Development Goals Report*. New York: United Nations.
- UN. (2014). *World Urbanization Prospects*. Economic and Social Affairs, UN Publications.
- UN. (2015). . *World Population Prospects: The 2015 Revision, Key Findings and Advance*. New York: UN, Economic and Social Affairs,

- UN ECOSOC. (2014). *Sustainable Urbanization*. ECOSOC, UN Publications
- UN Habitat. (2013). *The state of the world's cities 2012/2013*. Nairobi, Kenya: UN Habitat.
- UNEP. (2007). *Nairobi City Development Strategy Top Priority for 21st Century Future of the Kenyan Capital*. Kenya: UNEP.
- UNEP. (2009). *Kenya Atlas of Our Changing Environment*. Nairobi: United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP).
- UNEP. (2014). *Nairobi: Impacts of Urban Growth*. Nairobi, Kenya: UNEP/ DEWA/ GRID.
- UN-HABITAT. (2010). *Risk and Poverty in Urban Cities: A Case Study of African Informal Settlements*. Nairobi: UN publications.
- UN-Habitat. (2014). *The State of African Cities: Re-imagining sustainable urban transitions*. UN-Habitat. 978-92-1-133397-8
- URS Committee. (2011). *Urban Renewal Strategy; A District Based and Public Participatory Approach to Urban Renewal*. Hongkong: Urban Renewal Authority.
- Van, N. J. (1982). *Old Naledi: The Village Becomes a Town*. Toronto: James Lorimer and Company Publishers.
- Walmsley, R. (1957). *Nairobi: The Geography of a New City*. Nairobi: East African Literature Bureau.
- Wang, P. C. (1990). "Some Thoughts on the Preservation of Historical and Cultural Cities". In *China City Planning Review*, Vol.1, pp. 53-58.
- Weru, J. (2011). Resettlement Advisory Services for the Review of the Relocation Action Plan (RAP) in Kibera and Mukuru. Final Report. Retrieved from <http://documents.worldbank.org/curated/en/543631468008098258>
- White, T. (1948). *Nairobi, Master Plan for a Colonial Capital: A Report prepared for the Municipal Council of Nairobi*. London: HMSO.
- Williams, B. (1979). "Public Housing in Hong Kong,". In *Housing Review Sept.-Oct.* Vol 1 pp. 133-135.
- Yeh. (1990). "Public and Private Partnership in Urban Redevelopment in Hong Kong,". In *Third World Planning Review*, 12 (4) pp. 361-383.

APPENDICES

APPENDIX 1: QUESTIONNAIRE

INTRODUCTION

My name is **Monyenye Oremo**, a Masters student of Environmental Management in The Pan African University (Life and Earth Sciences including Health and Agriculture). As a pre-requisite requirement for the award of a master's degree in the above mentioned field, I am supposed to conduct a research on a topic/concept in the same field, approved by the Board of Postgraduates studies. The Board has therefore given me a go ahead to conduct an academic research on "Urban Renewal and Environmental Management". As such I am requesting you to fill the questionnaire so that I can get the necessary information for the success of my research. I assure you that the information you are going to provide shall be kept confidential by the researcher and will only be used for research purposes only.

DO NOT WRITE YOUR NAME ANYWHERE IN THIS QUESTIONNAIRE.

(Please tick as appropriate)

1. GENERAL INFORMATION

Area of residence a) Makongeni [] b) Mbotela [] c) Kianda [] d) Soweto []

2. SOCIO-ECONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS

Gender a) Male [] b) Female []

Age in years a) Less than 20 [] b) 20-25 [] c) 26-30 [] d) 31-35 [] e) 36-40 [] f) 41-45 [] g) 45 and above []

Marital Status a) Single [] b) Married [] c) Widowed [] d) Separated []

Level of Education a) Primary [] b) Secondary [] c) certificate [] d) Diploma []
e) 1st Degree [] f) Masters [] g) PhD [] h) Non formal education []

Religion a) Christianity [] b) Islam [] c) Traditional []

d) Other specify.....

Occupation a) Student [] b) Farming [] c) Craftsmanship [] d) Trading [] e) Retiree []

f) Private Sector Employment [] g) Public sector employment [] h) Unemployed []

Average Monthly Income (in KSH)

3. HOUSING AND HOUSING CHARACTERISTICS BEFORE RENEWAL

Type of house and number of occupants

TYPE OF PREVIOUS HOUSE	(Tick appropriately)	Number of occupants
Single		
Bedsitter		
One bedroom		
Two bedroom		
Three bedroom		
Other (Specify)		

Nature of occupancy a) Owner occupied [] b) Rented [] c) Free [] e) Other []

If rented, how much did you use to pay monthly as rent (in Ksh).....

Age of building (in yrs.) a) Below 10 [] b) 10-19 [] c) 20-29 [] d) 30 and above []
e) Don't know []

Materials used for wall construction a) Mud [] b) Stone [] c) Timber []
d) Others specify.....

Roofing materials a) Aluminium Sheet [] b) Asbestos (Tiles) []
c) Corrugated Iron Sheet [] d) others (specify)

Structural condition of the building a) Physically sound [] b) Needing minor repairs []
c) Needing major repairs [] d) Dilapidated []

What is your view concerning the old state? a) Very good [] b) good [] c) fair [] d) not good []

4. BASIC URBAN ENVIRONMENTAL SERVICES

4.1 WATER SUPPLY

Source of water

PERIOD	Source Purpose	County Council	Borehole	Communal Well	River/ Stream	Bottled Water	Local water vendors
Previous	Source of drinking water						
	Source of cooking and washing water						
Current	Source of drinking water						
	Source of cooking and washing water						

If piped water from County council/borehole, how regular is the supply

Interval Period	Daily	Once per week	Twice per Week	Not at all	Others specify
Previous					
Current					

Do you pay for piped water?

	YES	No	If yes how much in Ksh, per month?
Before Renewal			
After Renewal			

What is the distance of water source (in metres) to the house?

Distance	0-50	51-100	101-200	201-500	Over 500	Don't know
Previous						
Current						

What is your view concerning water supply in your new area?

Very good [] b) Good [] c) Fair [] d) Not good at all []

(Comment).....

4.2 MARKET

Where is the nearest retail shop for daily supplies in (metres)?

Distance	0-50	51-100	101-200	201-500	Over 500
Previous					
Current					

Describe the market environment

Status	Very Clean and hygienic	Clean and hygienic	Fairly Clean and hygienic	Not clean and hygienic at all
Previous				
Current				

4.3 WASTE MANAGEMENT

What method was/is used for waste collection?

Method	County council	Private collector	Open dumping	Open burning	Others specify
Previous					
Current					

How Frequent is/was the waste being collected?

Frequency	Daily	Once Weekly	Twice week a	Not at all	Others (please specify)
Previous					
Current					

What is your view concerning the management of waste in this area?

Very good [] b) Good [] c) Fair [] d) Not good at all []

4.4 DRAINAGE

What was your mode of toilet usage previously?

a) Per household [] b) Communal []

What types of toilet facility did/do you have?

Type of toilet \ Period	Pit Latrine	Public	Bucket method	Closet
Previous				
Current				

Type of drainage system?

Type of Drainage \ Period	Sewer line	Treatment plant	No drainage at all
Previous			
Current			

What is your perception about the general condition of drainage system in your area?

\ Period	Very good	good	Fair	Not good at all
Previous				
Current				

4.5 HEALTH

Any cases of outbreak of diseases?

Before Renewal Yes [] No []

After Renewal Yes [] No []

If Yes, what disease case was it?

	Malaria	Typhoid	Cholera	Amoeba	Others (Please specify)
Previous					
Current					

Which is/are the nearby health facilities?

\ Period	Dispensary	Community Health Centre	Public Health centre	Informal provision
Previous				
Current				

What is your view concerning the state of these facilities in your area?

	Very good	good	Fair	Not good at all
Previous				
Current				

4.6 ENERGY

What is your major source of energy supply?

KPLC [] b) Kerosene [] c) Solar [] e) Other []

If Other, Please specify.....

What have you been using for cooking and heating?

	Electricity	Charcoal	firewood	LPG	Others	If Other, Please specify
Previous						
Current						

4.7 SECURITY and ACCESSIBILITY

From your own point of view, how can you rate and compare this place in terms of security level?

	Very Secure	Secure	Fairly secure	Not secure
Previous				
Current				

Availability of police post (s) in the neighbourhood? Yes [] No []

Do you have a problem in accessing your locality? Yes [] No []

If yes, what makes your locality to be inaccessible?

	Lack of access road	Poor drainage	Lack of adequate development control mechanisms	Other	If Other, Please specify
Previous					
Current					

4.8 FIRE SERVICES

Availability of a fire station in the area? Yes [] No []

Cases of fire outbreak

	Weekly	Monthly	Annually	Irregular/unpredictable
Previous				
Current				

4.9 PRESERVATION

Which of these recreational/cultural facilities do/did you have in your neighbourhood?

	Library	Tombs/ Graves	Art galleries	Historic buildings	Museum	Sport facilities	Monument	Shrines
Previous								
Current								

What is your view concerning the state of these facilities?

	Very good	good	fair	Not good at all
Previous				
Current				

5. ENVIRONMENTAL AWARENESS

Availability of information to manage the environment?

Before Renewal Yes [] No []

After Renewal Yes [] No []

If yes, through which media do you get the information?

	Posters	rallies	Mass media	Volunteer groups	County Council
<u>Previous</u>					
<u>Current</u>					

According to you, where have you averagely received more sensitization as to manage the environment?

Previous place [] Current place []

APPENDIX 2: FOCUS GROUP DISCUSSIONS

Perception of housing and housing characteristics both in the new and old areas.

Experience of the Project Affected Persons (PAPS). (Environmental, Social and Economic/ Fate of the slum Structure Owners).

Views concerning water supply in the new area verses the old area. (Specific water vendors/ Coping with water issues in the new area).

General Perception towards their new market environment. (Specific markets in their area/ Influence of RAP on the market environment).

Perception on waste management in the new area. (Influence of RAP on the market environment/ Specific waste management private collectors/ Attitude of PAP towards waste management).

Views on the drainage system in the old area verses the new area.

Perception towards the health facilities in the new area. (Specific health facilities, both private and public/ Emerging health issues in the new area/ Perception towards security of the new area)

Plans put to maximize security. (Gating, fencing system/ Service Providers if any).

Views on heritage preservation, and recreational facilities in the neighbourhood. (Usability/ Accessibility)

Plans put to ensure the environment is kept clean and safe always. (Methods of sensitization/ Future plans)

Public participation in the whole process.

Maintenance operations in the area. (Water supply/ Energy supply/ Drainage systems/ Security systems/ Waste management/ Health Services/ RAP Buildings).

Highlight of Results

Water supply is not consistent and because it's a daily need, PAPs are forced to buy water from the water vendors in both situations, who charge almost 20 KES for a jericane of water. An upgrade of water tanks within the area is needed to cope with the water challenges.

The market being located nearby, most people prefer to go to the market they used to go. The RAP project also has provision for business stalls, which are generally more hygienic compared to the open air market. Besides, the general market environment has improved, even because of the National Youth Service (NYS) cleaning services.

Chances of contracting diseases has reduced, this is evident in the improvement of environment condition (clean water and better air to breathe). Drainage system has also improved as there is no open sewer lines, has led to reduction of dirty water related diseases; cholera, malaria etc..

Waste collection is currently done by private collectors who dispose wastes to designated dumping sites. In the previous residence, people largely practiced open dumping system, and all forms of waste were just thrown anywhere along the railway line. In current location waste management is now a personal responsibility, done per household. There is more information on how to collect waste and manage environment. Plastic paper bags are provided by the officials chosen by the committee of Soweto East Railway Residential Association (SERRA), to ensure that the environment is clean.

Family sizes is also an issue in the new design; large families being housed in small houses. The family structure has been disrupted as many have been forced to look for other accommodation elsewhere to cater for the shelter of remaining family members. Life has generally improved especially for the young generations as compared to the elderly.

Private security firms are contracted to take care of security issues and in regard to this, a payment of KES 500 is contributed by every household monthly. Thus security is much better in the new area of residence. In the previous area, security was reinforced through 'Nyumba Kumi Initiative' in which people clustered together and enhanced their security either through gating themselves or employing security personnel.

No library or recreational facility around, available ones are far from the new site of relocation. Children currently are using the open space outside for playing unlike in the previous residence where they use to play along the roads.

Houses are generally better and in good condition with no leaking roofs, or running sewer lines under floor of houses as in the previous location.

APPENDIX 3: KEY INFORMANT SCHEDULE

Procedure for the conduction of the UR projects in Makongeni, Mbotela and Kibera areas and their basis.

Challenges of implementing Urban Renewal Strategies in the area.

Consideration for environmental design.

Maintenance operations in the area.

Policies and legal frameworks enshrouding the urban renewal programs

Ideas about people's experiences towards various strategies employed in the area.

Highlight of Results

Refer to section 1.7.2.1 for the procedure of the RAP project

Challenge of implementing the project were rather political and legal based, from the side of the Government or social based in terms of fraud of PAPs' identification.

The design considered environmental design, including proper drainage and sanitation issues, provision of water meter for every household, and maintenance operations are segment based. Public participation was effected and the Project Affected Persons were involved even in the process of construction in terms of providing labour.

APPENDIX 4: OTHER FIGURES

Figure A: Scope of project in Kibera Source; RAP Files, 2014

Figure B (1): Scope of project in Mukuru (A) Source; RAP Files, 2014

Figure B (2): Scope of project in Mukuru (B) Source; RAP Files, 2014

Figure B (3): Scope of project in Mukuru (C); Source; RAP Files, 2014

APPENDIX 5: PLANS

Plan A: A Side view of Relocation Units. Source; RAP Files, 2014

APPENDIX 6: DAILY NATION NEWS EXCERPT

REPUBLIC OF KENYA

COUNTY GOVERNMENT OF MOMBASA

REQUEST FOR PROPOSALS FOR THE URBAN RENEWAL AND REDEVELOPMENT OF OLD ESTATES WITHIN MOMBASA COUNTY THROUGH JOINT VENTURE PARTNERSHIPS

TENDER NO: CGM/PRO/T/15/2015-2016

TIME EXTENSION ANNOUNCEMENT

With reference to the County Government of Mombasa tender notice vide no. **CGM/PRO/T/15/2015-2016**, dated: 3/02/2016 for **Phase 1** published on www.mombasa.go.ke.

The closing date has been extended up to **31ST MARCH, 2016 AT 1030 HOURS EAST AFRICAN TIME** for tender submission. All other terms and conditions are same (**except last date of Tender Submission and item 4.0 of the Appendix to Instruction to Bidders**).

All Bidders for Phase 1 and 2 are also requested to download and fill the Interested Bidders Registration Form from the County website www.mombasa.go.ke, and return it via email at bernard.thuku@ssmalonza.co.ke

Bidders interested in conducting site visits are requested to contact: **Ms. Sophie Ismail** on +254722502050; or **Mr. Bernard Thuku** on +254716171871.

COUNTY SECRETARY,
COUNTY GOVERNMENT OF MOMBASA.